

The genus *Haplocochlias* (Gastropoda, Skeneidae)

El género *Haplocochlias* (Gastropoda, Skeneidae)

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RESUMEN

Se estudian las especies conocidas del género *Haplocochlias* Carpenter, 1864, actualmente incluidas en la familia Skeneidae. Se han estudiado un total de 29 taxones, de los cuales 17 eran previamente conocidos, 11 se describen como especies nuevas y una más se queda sin nombre específico. Cada una de las especies se ilustra mediante fotografías de microscopio electrónico de barrido, clarificando su identidad y discutiendo su variabilidad específica, cuando esto es posible. Se aportan nuevos datos sobre el hábitat, distribución y rango batimétrico de algunas de estas especies. *Fossarus (Gottoina) compacta* Dall, 1889, *Parviturbo calidimaris* Pilsbry & McGinty, 1945, *Liotia erici* Strong & Hertlein, 1939, *Homalopoma concepcionensis* Lowe, 1935, *Parviturbo francesae* Pilsbry & McGinty, 1945, *Cyclostrema turbinum* Dall, 1889 y *Fossarus (Gottoina) bella* Dall, 1889 son transferidos en el presente trabajo al género *Haplocochlias*. Se rechaza la supuesta sinonimia de *Haplocochlias onaneyi* con *Haplocochlias williami*. Se designa un lectotipo para la especie *Fossarus (Gottoina) compacta* Dall, 1889. En un apéndice se comentan las especies fósiles y otros taxones (*Gottoina* y *Lophocochlias*) relacionados o parecidos con el género en estudio, mostrando sus especies tipo.

ABSTRACT

The known species of the genus *Haplocochlias* Carpenter, 1864, currently included in the family Skeneidae, are studied. We have included a total of 29 species, of which 17 were previously known, 11 are described as new species, and one more is kept without a specific name. Each species is figured with scanning electron micrographs, and its variability discussed, when possible. New information on habitat, distribution, and bathymetric range of some species is provided. *Fossarus (Gottoina) compacta* Dall, 1889, *Parviturbo calidimaris* Pilsbry & McGinty, 1945, *Liotia erici* Strong & Hertlein, 1939, *Homalopoma concepcionensis* Lowe, 1935, *Parviturbo francesae* Pilsbry & McGinty, 1945, *Cyclostrema turbinum* Dall, 1889 and *Fossarus (Gottoina) bella* Dall, 1889 are here transferred to the genus *Haplocochlias*. The alleged synonymy of *Haplocochlias onaneyi* with *Haplocochlias williami* is rebutted. A lectotype is designated for *Fossarus (Gottoina) compacta* Dall, 1889. In an appendix, fossil species and other taxa (*Gottoina* and *Lophocochlias*) related to or resembling *Haplocochlias* are commented on, and their type species illustrated.

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INTRODUCTION

According to HICKMAN & MCLEAN (1990: 146), there are two shallow-water genera in the family Skeneidae which possess a thickened aperture: *Haplocochlias* Carpenter, 1864 and *Parviturbo* Pilsbry & McGinty, 1945, both distributed in the eastern Pacific and western and southern Atlantic. Both genera share anatomical and radular characters, which was why HICKMAN & MCLEAN (1990) united them as the *Parviturbo* - *Haplocochlias* group in the family Skeneidae.

The *Haplocochlias*-*Parviturbo* group of species are interstitial, usually sublittoral or infralittoral. Like European skeneid species of the genera *Skenea*, *Skeneoides*, *Dikoleps* or *Lodderena*, they tend to live in relatively shallow water in the interstices of the gravel on rocky beaches, in the interstices of coarse sediments under stones, in maërl, coralline sediments and in *Laminaria* beds on rocks. An element common to many of these habitats is the presence of calcareous algae.

From the species of *Haplocochlias*, those of *Parviturbo* can be differentiated because they have more prominent spiral cords in short number (usually 8 on the last whorl), sometimes some of them may be nodose and the columella is not widened at its base and not reflected towards the umbilicus.

The shells are so minute that it is virtually impossible to distinguish them in their natural environment. For this reason these species can only be collected through sampling of algae, coralline sand, gravel, and other sediments. In most samples only empty shells are found.

Since CARPENTER (1864) created the genus *Haplocochlias* with *H. cyclophoreus* as sole included species, a total of 8 species have been described: two (*H. lucasensis* and *H. cyclophoreus*) on the Eastern Pacific coast and seven (*H. swifti*, *H. ortizi*, *H. nunezi*, *H. cubensis*, *H. moolenbeeki*, *H. risoneideneryae* and *H. williami*) on the shores of the Western Atlantic. One more species, *Haplocochlias costaricensis* Robinson, 1991 is denoted by an unavailable name.

We have reviewed two species originally placed by DALL (1889) in the genus

Gottoina: *Fossarus* (*Gottoina*) *bella* and *Fossarus* (*Gottoina*) *compacta*, comparing them with *Gottoina sulcifera* A. Adams, 1863, the type species of the genus, and reassigned them to *Haplocochlias*. Likewise, we have revised and figured *Haplocochlias* (*Lophocochlias*) *minutissimus* Pilsbry, 1921, originally described in *Haplocochlias*, and consider *Lophocochlias* Pilsbry, 1921 as full genus. We also have revised the species placed hitherto in the genus *Parviturbo* Pilsbry & McGinty, 1945 and in our opinion four of them (*Parviturbo conceptionensis*, *P. erici*, *P. calidimaris* and *P. francesae*) should be included in *Haplocochlias* due to their morphological affinity with other species of this genus.

The scarcity of works related with species of the genus *Haplocochlias*, the difficulties often encountered in their specific differentiation, the errors in the identification of previously named species due to lack of appropriate illustrations or their poor quality, has prompted us to carry out the present work. To do this, we have reviewed all known species, both Pacific and Atlantic, comparing the material studied with the type material and presenting as much information as possible for each species: habitat, bathymetry, geographical distribution and differential characteristics.

There are few fossil species, and although this is not the focus of this work, we present some information in Appendix 1. Some genera have been considered related to *Haplocochlias*, but, after the study of their type species, we concluded that they (*Gottoina* and *Lophocochlias*) are not related and we discuss them in Appendix 2.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Most of the material studied in the present work was obtained from sediments collected by diving or from dredgings and later sorted under a stereoscopic microscope. Consequently most of the material is composed of empty shells from the shell grit; occasionally a shell with soft parts could be obtained. An important part of the material studied is from Cuba, and

this material was mainly obtained from collections by the second author at Cienfuegos Bay and later deposited mostly in the MHNS. For this reason, at the beginning of this study we only examined Cuban shells. Subsequently we included the material obtained by the third author on several trips to Yucatan, Mexico, Guatemala, Nicaragua, and south and west Cuba. Finally, we received material collected by Colin Redfern from the Bahamas, Marlo Krisberg, Emilio García and Jacques Pelorce and an important amount from the collection of Harry G. Lee, all of which considerably amplified the study in terms of biodiversity and zoogeography. We studied types and other material in other private collections and several museums.

The description of the protoconch whorls was made following the method of VERDUIN (1976) in which the whorls are counted based on a concept of the nucleus.

Abbreviations:

AMNH American Museum of Natural History, New York, USA
 ANSP Academy of Natural Sciences, Philadelphia, USA
 BMSM Bailey-Matthews Shell Museum, Sanibel, Florida
 CITMA Ministerio de Ciencia y Tecnología y Medio Ambiente, Havana, Cuba
 FLMNH Florida Museum Natural History, Gainesville, USA
 FMNH Field Museum of Natural History, Chicago, USA
 IES Instituto de Ecología y Sistemática, Havana, Cuba
 LACM Los Angeles County Museum, USA
 MCZ Museum of Comparative Zoology, Cambridge, Massachusetts, USA

MHN “Carlos de la Torre” de Holguín, Cuba
 MHNS Museo de Historia Natural “Luis Iglesias”, University of Santiago de Compostela (coll. E. Rolán), Spain
 MNCN Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Madrid, Spain
 MNH of Santa Cruz de Tenerife, Canarias
 MNHN Muséum National d’Histoire Naturelle, Paris, France
 MPH Museo Poey, Havana, Cuba
 NHMUK Natural History Museum of the United Kingdom (formerly BM (NH)), England
 NMR Natural Museum of Rotterdam, The Netherlands
 SDSNH San Diego Society of Natural History, USA
 UFRPE Universidade Federal Rural, Pernambuco, Brazil
 USNM National Museum of Natural History, Washington, USA
 ZMA Zoological Museum, Amsterdam, (now Naturalis, Leiden), The Netherlands
 CCR collection of Colin Redfern, Boca Raton, Florida, USA
 CEG collection of Emilio Garcia, Louisiana, USA
 CFG collection of Raúl Fernández-Garcés, Cienfuegos, Cuba
 CFR collection of Federico Rubio, Valencia, Spain
 CHL collection of Harry G. Lee, Florida, USA
 CJP collection of Jacques Pelorce, Le Grau de Roi, France
 SEM scanning electron microscopy/microscope/micrograph
 sp specimen with soft parts
 s empty shell
 j juvenile
 f fragment

SYSTEMATIC PART

Superfamily TURBINOIDEA Rafinesque, 1815

Family SKENEIDAE Clark, 1851

Genus *Haplocochlias* Carpenter, 1864

Haplocochlias Carpenter, 1864. *Annals and Magazine of Natural History*, (3)13: 476 [Type species by monotypy: *Haplocochlias cyclophoreus* Carpenter, 1864, Cape St. Lucas, Mexico; Recent species].

Original description: "Testa Colloniam simulans, sed haud margaritacea: aperture circularis, varicose: columella haud callosa".

KEEN (1971): "Globose shells with fine spiral sculpture, narrow umbilicus and thickened outer lip".

HICKMAN & McLEAN (1990) provided a detailed description of the group consisting of the genera *Haplocochlias* and *Parviturbo*, based on the radula of both genera and the external anatomy of a preserved although contracted specimen of *Haplocochlias swifti*, which was dehydrated by the technique of critical-point and observed under SEM:

"The shell is small to minute (2–5 mm in height), narrowly umbilicate, non-nacreous, white, with strong spiral sculpture, a circular generating curve, and a complete peristome that is terminally thickened. The operculum is completely corneous, multispiral with a short growing edge, and not enveloped exteriorly by the foot.

The ctenidium is apparently monopectinate, with at least 30 elongate leaflets, and lacks a free tip and bursicles. Cephalic tentacles are relatively long, extending well forward of the snout tip. The cephalic tentacles are flattened dorsally, with micropapillae extending laterally. There are three pairs of long epipodial tentacles that also bear micropapillae.

"The radulae of *Haplocochlias* and *Parviturbo* are of the same plan as lower turbinids, although the rachidian tooth is unusually broad, exceeding the combined width of all the adjacent lateral teeth. The laterals are well developed and are similar size and shape, with the characteristic bend in the shaft, and with long overhanging cusps with finely serrate outer margins and simple inner margins. The lower shafts and bases are relatively thin and produced into strongly overlapping flanges. This is the only skeneiform group that has a distinct lateromarginal plate, a well-developed structure that is fused to the first marginal tooth shaft and cusp. In addition to the within-interactions of the lateromarginal plates with the outer laterals and the between-row interactions of the plates with one another, there is a particularly complex interaction with the inner marginal teeth. The base of

the plate extends behind and in front of the lower portion of the shafts of the inner marginals, providing the potential for transmitting forces and promoting alignment during both protraction and retraction of the radula. The inner marginal teeth are not enlarged, and the marginals are all of the same form with long, narrow, strongly overhanging cusps and a well-developed food-collecting groove".

"Many more data are needed before the relationships of the skeneiform taxa can be analyzed. Data on the condition of the ctenidium are of special importance. The ctenidium has been examined in only one genus in addition to *Haplocochlias* (McLean, personal observation). Preserved material of *Dillwynella* provided by Marshall, has revealed a gill that is similar to that of *Haplocochlias* and extends this set of three characters (monopectinate condition, loss of bursicles, and lack of free tip) beyond the shallow-water eastern Pacific and western Atlantic clade".

"Other characters that may be of significance in evaluating monophyly are the shape of the anterior end of the foot, the length and shape of the cephalic and epipodial tentacles, and arrangement and prominence of macropapillae on the cephalic and epipodial tentacles. For example, the "narrow auricles" described on the foot of *Parviturbo* by PILSBRY & MCGINTY (1945) need to be compared in live or carefully relaxed and preserved material with the "lateral points" that FRETTER & GRAHAM (1977) have described as elongated into "tentaculiform outgrowths", and these in turn must be compared with the epipodial outgrowths of different types that occur in a variety of Trochacean clades."

A short condensed description of the genus would be: The shell is small to minute (1–6 mm in height), turbiniform, with a closed to narrowly opening umbilicus with spiral cordlets inside. Protoconch $\frac{3}{4}$ whorl, smooth or with spiral cordlets. Teleoconch with a rounded or slightly angulous periphery; ornamentation formed by numerous spiral cords and axial striae with micro tubercles on their interspaces. Aperture prosocline, peristoma continuous; columella sometimes reflected towards the

Figure 1. *Haplocochlias arrondoii* spec. nov. A, B: radula. Faro de los Colorados, Cienfuegos, Cuba; C: operculum.

Figura 1. *Haplocochlias arrondoii* spec. nov. A, B: rádula. Faro de los Colorados, Cienfuegos, Cuba; C: opérculo.

umbilicus, widened at its base with the presence in some species of a depressed area in the crossing point with the umbilical cord. Outer lip wide or fine, crenulated or expanded frontally.

CARPENTER (1864) mentions about *Haplocochlias*: "Its affinities may be with *Ethalia* H. & A. Adams, 1854." The genus was placed in the Cyclostrematidae by FISCHER (1885) and subsequently in the family Skeneidae by KNIGHT *ET AL.* in MOORE (1960). The genus *Gelasinostoma* Gardner, 1947, from the Plio-Pleistocene of the western Atlantic (Loxahatchee, Florida) seems to be close to *Haplocochlias*.

Haplocochlias means "unadorned snail", possibly alluding to the lack of conspicuous ornamentation noted by CARPENTER (1864) on the type species (*H. cyclophoreus*) on the teleoconch surface "minutissime spiraliter striolata". However, after examining the ornamentation in most of the species in this genus, we can conclude that the meaning of the word that defines the genus is not the most appropriate.

For a better identification and differentiation of the species studied, we have grouped them by morphological affinity. At the same time we have created an identification key with the intention of providing a useful tool for species determination.

Considering the morphology of their shells, and after a comparison with *Gottoina sulcifera* A. Adams, 1863, type species of the genus (Figs. 43 A-D), we have transferred to *Haplocochlias* two species described by DALL (1889): *Fossarus (Gottoina) bella* and *Fossarus (Gottoina) compacta*, both from the East coast of the United States.

The fundamental differences between the species of both genera are: the shell of *Gottoina* is imperforate, has an arched inner lip and the outer lip with a crenulated margin, all of which are characters not present in the species placed by Dall in *Gottoina*. One must consider that prior to the description of these two species, DALL (1889) wrote: "We have now to add two small species, which seem to range from Florida to Cape Hatteras, having been obtained off the coast of North Carolina, in less than 100 fms (183 m), by the U. S Fish Commission. They appear to belong to the subgenus *Gottoina* of A. Adams, which is described as imperforate, solid, and ornamented with spiral sculpture. I have not seen a typical specimen of *Gottoina*, which, moreover, has not been figured, so I refer these species to it on account of their apparent relation to *Fossarus* and the description of *Gottoina* aforesaid".

The fact that DALL (1889) admitted not having seen any typical specimen of

Gottoina and that it had not been figured, indicates that his inclusion of both species in the subgenus was based exclusively on the literal description.

For a better comparative study, we have separated the species into six groups based on morphological characters.

cyclophoreus group

Remarks: The species included in this group are mainly characterized by the robustness of the shell, by having a completely smooth protoconch, without spiral cordlets, and by a very thick aper-

ture. With the exception of *Haplocochlias risoneideneryae*, all of them lack axial striae in the spaces between the teleoconch cords; only thin lines of growth that can be observed there.

Haplocochlias cyclophoreus Carpenter, 1864 (Figures 2, 3)

Haplocochlias cyclophoreus Carpenter, 1864. *Annals and Magazine of Natural History*, (3)13: 476. [Type locality: Cape St. Lucas, Pacific coast of Mexico].

Type material: Syntypes deposited in AMNH (n° 18112) and in NHMUK, in the Cuming Collection. Not examined.

Other material examined: Mexico, Pacific coast: 1 s, Punta Mita, Nayarit, West México (CHL); 17 s, Pulmo Bay, Baja California, 5-20 ft (1.5-6 m) on boulders and ledges, some coral (LACM 66-19); 18 s, Sayulita, about 23 miles (37 kms) north of Puerto Vallarta, Nayarit, intertidal (LACM 70-4); 7 s, El Chileno (Rancho El Tule), Baja California Sur, intertidal (LACM 70-52); 3 j, W side of Ceralvo Island, Baja California, 30-50 ft (9-15 m) (LACM 71-24); 11 s, Bahia Escondida, Baja California Sur, intertidal (LACM 71-31).

Description: Original description in CARPENTER (1864: 476): "*Testa compacta, parva, solidiore; albida, sed pallide aurantiaca; anf. v., rapide augmentibus, suturis impressis; tota superficie minutissime spiraliter striolata, nitida; apertura rotundata; peritremate continuo, incrassato, extus varicoso; labio distincto; axi t. jun. umbilicata, adultae lacunata. Long. 19, long. spir. 06, lat. 2 poll., div. 100°*". The best illustration is in PALMER (1958, pl. 65, figs. 1-2), two syntypes from Cape St. Lucas.

Shell turbiniform, globose, solid, of white-yellowish colour, spire formed by 4 $\frac{3}{4}$ rapidly-expanding whorls, separated by a distinct suture. The protoconch has almost $\frac{3}{4}$ whorl, is completely smooth, measuring about 220 μ m in diameter and there is neither a varix nor any thickening at its terminus. The teleoconch has 4 spiral whorls, with spiral cords of regular size, scarcely prominent, which are distributed across shell; the spaces between cords are covered by microtubercles and by regu-

larly-spaced axial grooves that disappear on the last whorl, leaving only growth lines. At the beginning of each whorl, we count 4 cords on the first, 7 on the second, 14 on the third, and about 42 at the beginning of the fourth. The aperture is rounded and the peristome continuous, very thick and slightly crenulated in the columellar area. The outer lip is thickened on its outer margin by the presence of spiral cords and rough, very tight growth lines. The reflection of the columella and a thin parietal callus almost close the umbilicus, which is delimited by a spiral cord and is reduced to a narrow fissure, with only growth lines inside. Some specimens show a strong parietal callus which is expanded and together with the columella totally closes the umbilicus (Fig. 3A-B).

Dimensions: height, 5 mm; diameter, 5.2 mm. The specimen photographed in Figure 2 measures 5.15 mm in height and 5.35 mm in maximum diameter.

Figure 2. *Haplocochlias cyclophoreus* Carpenter, 1864. A-C: shell, 5.15 x 5.35 mm, Punta Mita, Nayarit, Pacific coast of Mexico (CHL); D: apical view; E: protoconch; F, G: microsculpture and detail of last whorl, same shell.

Figura 2. Haplocochlias cyclophoreus Carpenter, 1864. A-C: concha, 5,15 x 5,35 mm, Punta Mita, Nayarit, costa pacífica de México (CHL); D: vista apical; E: protoconcha; F, G: microescultura y detalle de la última vuelta, misma concha.

Figure 3. *Haplocochlias cyclophoreus* Carpenter, 1864. A: shell, diameter 4.75 mm, dorsal view, Escondida Bay, Baja California Sur, Mexico (LACM); B: shell, diameter 4.6 mm, apertural view, Pulmo Bay, Mexico; C: protoconch, same shell as A; D: microsculpture of the last whorl, same shell as B.

Figura 3. Haplocochlias cyclophoreus Carpenter, 1864. A: concha, diámetro 4,75 mm, vista dorsal, Bahía Escondida, Baja California Sur, México (LACM); B: concha, diámetro 4,6 mm, vista apertural, Bahía Pulmo, Baja California, México; C: protoconcha, misma concha que A; D: microescultura de la última vuelta, misma concha que B.

Habitat: Intertidal to 10 m (KEEN, 1971). Under rocks, between 2 and 5 meters. The studied samples are in the most part intertidal, have been found down to 15 m deep; they live on boulders and ledges with some coral.

Distribution: Cape St. Lucas, Mexico (CARPENTER, 1864). Magdalena Bay, Cape San Lucas and Espiritu Santo Island, Baja California; Tres Marias Islands and south to Banderas Bay, Jalisco, Mexico (KEEN, 1971; ABBOTT, 1974).

Remarks: CARPENTER (1864) remarked: "When laid on its base, this shell resembles *Helicina*; but the mouth is more like *Cyclophorus*. The young shell is semi-transparent, and resembles a *Vitrinella* with thickened lip".

In the absence of illustrations of the species described by CARPENTER (1864), PALMER (1958) published a work that illustrated the type material of the species from the West Coast (San Diego to British Columbia), including the type locality and catalogue number of each.

Figure 4. *Haplocochlias lucasensis* (Strong, 1934). A, B: shell, 1.60 mm in diameter, Cape San Lucas, Baja California, Mexico (CHL); C: partial view of the protoconch, same shell; D: microsculpture.

Figura 4. *Haplocochlias lucasensis* (Strong, 1934). A, B: concha, 1,60 mm de diámetro, Cabo San Lucas, Baja California, México (CHL); C: vista parcial de la protoconcha, misma concha; D: microescultura.

Given that *Haplocochlias cyclophoreus* is the type species of the genus by monotypy, it is essential to point out the characters that serve to identify the group and characterize the genus.

After the examination of numerous samples we could see that in the last $\frac{3}{4}$ of the last whorl the spiral cords are widening, the axial striae disappear and the interspaces between cords are reduced to narrow grooves, where only

micro tubercles can be seen. The species is characterized by its external lip with growth lines close together on the border of the lip.

H. cyclophoreus differs from its congeners by its larger size, the solidity of its shell, its smooth protoconch, the regularity and size of the spiral cords and their interspaces, by the characteristic thickened lip and its umbilicus, reduced to a small slit.

Figure 5. *Haplocochlias lucasensis* (Strong, 1934). A, B: shell, diameter 1.60 mm, Pulmo Bay, Baja California, Mexico (LACM 66-19); C: protoconch, same shell; D: protoconch of a juvenile.

Figura 5. *Haplocochlias lucasensis* (Strong, 1934). A, B: concha, diámetro 1,60 mm, Bahía Pulmo, Baja California, México (LACM 66-19); C: protoconcha, misma concha; D: protoconcha de un juvenil.

Haplocochlias lucasensis (Strong, 1934) (Figures 4, 5)

Liotia lucasensis Strong, 1934. *Transactions of the San Diego Society of Natural History*, 7 (37): 441, pl. 29, figs. 10-12. [Type locality: Cape San Lucas, Baja California, Pacific coast of Mexico].

Type material: Holotype in California Academy of Sciences (n° 5477). Not examined.

Other material examined: Mexico, Pacific coast: 1 sp, Cape San Lucas, Baja California, undersides of rocks at low tide line (CHL); 19 s, Rancho El Tule, Canelo Bay, Baja California, intertidal on rock boulders and ledges (LACM 66-15); 7 s, Rancho El Tule, Canelo Bay, Baja California, 15-30 ft (4.5-9 m), on large boulders and in rock crevices (LACM 66-16); 42 s, Pulmo Bay, Baja California, 5-20 ft (1.5-6 m), on boulders and ledges, some coral (LACM 66-19); 16 s, Isla de San Pedro Nolasco, Sonora, outside rock at south tip at 30-75 ft (9-23 m) (LACM 67-4); 5 s, W side of Ceralvo Island, Baja California, 15-20 ft (4.5-6 m) (LACM 71-25).

Description: This is the original description by STRONG (1934): "Shell minute, globose, shining white, of about three and a half slightly shouldered whorls and a

very minute flattened nucleus of a little over one whorl; sutures not excavated; spiral sculpture of fine, raised, smooth, spiral threads, of which four appear on the first

whorl, eight on the second and about twenty on the body whorl; axial sculpture absent; aperture circular, with a thick, continuous lip; umbilicus small. The type, which is one of about 200 more or less beach worn specimens, comes from Cape San Lucas and measures: height, 1.7; maximum diameter, 1.6 mm".

The protoconch has 3/4 whorl and a maximum diameter of 220 μ m. Despite the poor condition of the protoconch of the shell studied, we were able to observe a spiral cord (Fig. 4C) close to the suture. For this reason we have inferred that this species, like its congeners, has spiral cords on the protoconch.

Teleoconch with 3 whorls; ornamentation formed by slightly prominent spiral cords, narrower than their interspaces, no axial grooves, but numerous microtubercles completely covering the spaces between cords. There are 21 spiral cords at the beginning of the last whorl. Aperture rounded; columella arched, not reflected; outer lip with a sharp border, very thick inside, not crenulated. Umbilicus narrow and deep, fusiform, in its interior there are several growth lines.

Dimensions: holotype 1.7 mm high, 1.6 mm in diameter. Our material is similar in size.

Habitat: Intertidal to 10 m (KEEN, 1971; ABBOTT, 1974). The studied speci-

mens were distributed between intertidal and infralittoral areas, and their bathymetric range between 0 and 75 ft (23 m), on rock boulders and ledges and in rock crevices.

Distribution: Recorded from Cape San Lucas, Baja California, Mexico (STRONG, 1934); from San Pedro Nolasco Island and Guaymas, south to Cape San Lucas and Socorro Island, Revillagigedo Islands, Mexico (KEEN, 1971) and Gulf of California (ABBOTT, 1974).

Remarks: *Haplocochlias lucasensis* was described in the genus *Liotia*, and its author STRONG (1934) stated: "This minute species would seem to be entirely distinct from any of the other west coast species placed in the genus".

KNIGHT *ET AL.* (1960) placed it in *Haplocochlias*, considering the morphological characters of its shell quite similar to those of *H. cyclophoreus*. Indeed, *H. lucasensis* is very similar in its ornamentation and lip thickening to *H. cyclophoreus*, but it differs by its smaller size and less globose spire. Another species which presents a certain affinity in ornamentation is *H. cubensis*, but, in addition to the geographical distribution, the latter has a larger number of the spiral cords on the teleoconch whorls.

Haplocochlias compactus (Dall, 1889) (Figure 6)

Fossarus (*Gottoina*) *compacta* Dall, 1889. *Bulletin of the Museum of Comparative Zoology*, 18: 273, pl. 28, fig. 6. [Type locality from lectotype: Off Havana, Cuba, 153 m].

Type material: Syntype in MCZ (7462) here designated as lectotype, from off Havana, Cuba, 84 fathoms (153 m), examined. Nine paratypes from USFC sta. 2596 in USNM (94910), not examined.

Other material examined: USA: 1 s, (28° 4.57' N-90° 59.99' W), Louisiana, dredged at 87.9 m (CHL); 1 s, station D-1 (28° 3.43' N-92° 26.97' W), Louisiana, dredged at 71-74 m (CHL); 2 s, off Sombrero Light, Key Vaca, Monroe Co., Florida, dredged at 67 m (CHL); 1 s, station BIERFK-419, Carysfort reef, Florida Keys, Monroe Co., Florida, 79 m (FMNH, 333903); 1 s, station BIERFK-447, Key Colony Beach, Florida Keys, Monroe Co., Florida, 77 m (FMNH, 333881); 1 s, station BIERFK-445, Key Colony Beach, Florida Keys, Monroe Co., Florida, 57 m (FMNH, 333914).

Description: Original description in DALL (1889): "Shell small, white, compact, elevated, spirally sculptured, of about four and a half whorls including the nucleus; outline of the spire convex with hardly any rounding in of the whorls toward the suture,

which is nevertheless distinct and finely channelled. Radiating sculpture none, lines of growth not visible; spiral sculpture of fine, close, even, rounded threads, growing gradually smaller from the suture forward; there is no secondary grooving; there are about

Figure 6. *Haplocochlias compactus* (Dall, 1889). A: Lectotype of *Fossarus (Gottoina) compacta* Dall, 1889 (MCZ-7462); B-D: shell, diameter 1.70 mm, Louisiana, USA (28° 4.57' N-90° 59.99' W) (CHL); E: protoconch, same shell as D; F: microsculpture, same shell.

Figura 6. *Haplocochlias compactus* (Dall, 1889). A: Lectotipo de *Fossarus (Gottoina) compacta* Dall, 1889 (MCZ-7462); B-D: concha, diámetro 1,70 mm, Louisiana, EE. UU. (28° 4,57' N-90° 59,99' W) (CHL); E: protoconcha, misma concha que D; F: microescultura, misma concha.

twenty-five threads on the last whorl, but they vary in number and strength with the individual specimen; base full and rounded, imperforate; aperture rounded, pointed behind, and the angle filled with callus; callus continuous, thinnest on the columella. Alt. 2.3 mm.; max. diam. 2.0 mm."

Additional description: The protoconch has somewhat more than $\frac{3}{4}$ whorl, it measures about 220 μm in diameter and is completely smooth. Teleoconch composed of 2 $\frac{3}{4}$ whorls completely covered by spiral cords, usually narrower than their interspaces, which appear totally covered by microtubercles. In apertural view the examined shells have 21 and 23 spiral cords in the last whorl. Columella and outer lip reflected outward. At the confluence with the outer lip, the columella and umbilical cord become slightly expanded. Within the umbilicus, 1-2 cordlets can be seen.

Dimensions: Maximum reported size: 2.3 mm. The shell examined is 1.63 mm in height and 1.70 mm in diameter (H/D: 0.96).

Habitat: Based on the known bathymetric information, this is a species that lives in the circalittoral level, between 57 and 80 m depth, having also been found on the continental slope, between 89 and 195 m deep.

Distribution: USA: USFC sta. 2595, 2596, 2612, off North Carolina, 35.14°N to 23°N; 97°W to 75.09°W (DALL, 1889); Texas (ODÉ, 1987); Off North Carolina, and Florida Keys (ABBOTT, 1974). Cuba: Off Havana (type locality, leg. Sigsbee).

Remarks: The syntype of *Fossarus* (*Gottoina*) *compacta* Dall, 1889 (MCZ, 7462) (Fig. 6A), here designated as lectotype, is an adult specimen larger than those examined in the present work and which agrees with the original description in appearing imperforate. This seems due to the widening and reflection of the columella which close the umbilicus totally. In contrast, the studied samples are smaller and, even being adult, present a reduced umbilicus, and probably only in senile specimens, due to the larger size and reflection of the columella, the umbilicus becomes totally closed. This situation could be observed also in other species of the genus.

In our opinion, *Fossarus* (*Gottoina*) *compacta* should be moved to the genus *Haplocochlias* because of its similarity to *H. cyclophoreus* and *H. lucasensis*. The solidity of the shell, the completely smooth protoconch and a teleoconch entirely covered by spiral cords which lack axial grooves in their interspaces, support its transfer to *Haplocochlias*.

Haplocochlias risoneidenergyae Barros, Santos, Santos, Cabral & Acioli, 2002
(Figure 7)

Haplocochlias risoneidenergyae Barros, Santos, Santos, Cabral & Acioli, 2002. *Boletim Tecnico Cientifico do CEPENE*, 10 (1): 44, fig. 4 A-D. [Type locality: Fernando de Noronha, Pernambuco, Brazil].

Type material: 11 specimens in Museu de Malacologia da UFRPE (n° 7601). Not examined.

Material examined: Brazil: 2 s, off north Natal, Rio Grande do Norte State, taken in coral sand at 15-25 m (CHL).

Description: Original description in BARROS ET AL. (2002): "Concha pequena, turbinada. Protoconcha formada por uma volta e meia aproximadamente, de contornos amplamente convexos e de aspecto liso. Núcleo evidente, plano. Espira baixa, ornada por várias cordas espirais fortes e um ombro conspicuo. Umbílico parcialmente fechado,

lábio externo espesso, abertura arredondada, sutura pouco profunda, não canaliculada; linhas de crescimento e cicatrizes pouco evidentes. Anfractos inflados fortemente convexos.

Ornamentação axial inconspícua. Base curta e afilada desta com a parede umbilical. Diâmetro máximo: 4,2 mm".

Figure 7. *Haplocochlias risoneideneryae* Barros, Santos, Santos, Cabral & Acioli, 2002. A, B: shell, 4.52 × 4.30 mm, Rio Grande do Norte, Brazil (CHL); C: protoconch, same shell; D-F: microsculpture from the middle part of the last whorl.

Figura 7. Haplocochlias risoneideneryae Barros, Santos, Santos, Cabral & Acioli, 2002. A, B: concha, 4,52 × 4,30 mm, Rio Grande do Norte, Brasil (CHL); C: protoconcha, misma concha; D-F: microes-cultura de la parte mediana de la última vuelta.

The largest examined specimen measures 4.52 mm in height and 4.30 mm in diameter, and its spire is formed by 5 $\frac{1}{4}$ rapidly expanding whorls. The protoconch has $\frac{3}{4}$ whorl and is totally smooth, measuring about 200 μ m. The teleoconch is formed by 4 $\frac{1}{2}$ whorls, completely covered by spiral cords, with axial growth marks and microtubercles in the interspaces. In the apertural view 3-4 cords can be seen on the first whorl, 5 on the second, 8 on the third and 24 on the last one. The interspaces are wider than the cords and are completely covered by very closely placed fine axial grooves, especially on the last whorl. In the last half whorl, a fine spiral cordlet arises between the spiral cords, so the number of cords on the outer lip is much greater. Aperture rounded, slightly prosocline; outer lip very thick; many spiral cords on its external margin and a strong thickened lip can be observed, and on its inner margin there is fine denticulation; columella very wide at its base and reflected towards the umbilicus, covering it completely; parietal area covered by a thin callous coat.

Habitat: The type material comes from intertidal sediments. Other material examined was collected at depths between 15 and 25 m.

Distribution: Brazil: Fernando de Noronha, Pernambuco, Natal, and Rio Grande do Norte States.

Remarks: In its general appearance *Haplocochlias risoneideneryae* is quite similar to *H. cyclophoreus*, being oblong, thick, and having a very thickened outer lip, the protoconch being totally smooth. *Haplocochlias risoneideneryae* may be distinguished from *H. cyclophoreus* by having the umbilicus completely covered and the spaces between cords ornamented with fine axial striae which, on the last whorl, become very numerous; also its spire is more angulate. Despite being one of the larger species, the diameter of its protoconch is the smallest among the known species.

Until its description as a new species, *H. risoneideneryae* was identified as *H. swifti*. BARROS *ET AL.* (2002), in their figure 3 represent the supposed holotype of *H. swifti* Vanatta, 1913 for comparison; however, that figure is neither *H. swifti* nor the holotype (ANSP 10292). It is the shell shown in ABBOTT (1974, fig. 457) as *H. swifti*, but, by from its morphological characters, mainly the shape of the lip, it is probably *H. nunezi* or *H. moolenbeeki*. BARROS *ET AL.* (2002), in failing to verify the type material, perpetuated the error of ABBOTT (1974).

Haplocochlias multiliratus spec. nov. (Figure 8)

Type material: Holotype in LACM (3260) (Figs. 8A-B).

Other material examined: None.

Type locality: Small islets off Quepos, Puntarenas province, Costa Rica (9° 22' 12"N-84° 09' 15"W), 75 ft (23 m), gravel and cobble.

Etymology: The specific name alludes to the numerous cordlets of its sculpture.

Description: Shell of very small size, globose, turbiniform, wider than high (H/D: 0.82), spire formed by 3 $\frac{3}{4}$ rapidly increasing whorls. The protoconch has $\frac{3}{4}$ of whorl, is apparently smooth, measures 190 μ m and finishes in a varix. The teleoconch has 3 spiral whorls and is ornamented by spiral cords, axial striae and micro tubercles. In apertural view 3-4 cords on the first whorl can be seen, following with 5 on the second and 20-21 on the last one; from these, the upper

5 are more prominent and at the same time narrower than their interspaces, while the others are as wide as their interspaces. Distinct axial striae which do not form lamellae are distributed regularly in the spaces between the cords, except on the last half whorl, where the interspaces are narrower and the striae disappear, only being appreciable the micro tubercles.

Aperture rounded, prosocline; peristome continuous. Parietal area covered

Figure 8. *Haplocochlias multiliratus* spec. nov. A, B: holotype, diameter 1.94 mm, small islets off Quepos, Puntarenas province, Costa Rica; C: protoconch, apical view of the holotype; D, E: ornamentation detail of the last whorl, near the base.

Figura 8. *Haplocochlias multiliratus* spec. nov. A, B: holotipo, diámetro 1,94 m, islotes frente a Quepos, provincia de Puntarenas, Costa Rica; C: protoconcha, vista apical del holotipo; D, E: detalle de ornamentación de la última vuelta, cerca de la base.

by a strong callous coating; columella almost straight, wide, amplified at its base, not reflected towards the umbilicus; external lip very wide, not denticulate inside or crenulated in spite of the numerous spiral cordlets that originate on the last half whorl. Umbilicus wide, deep, delimited by a strong spiral cord; in its interior 5-6 spiral cordlets and marked growth lines can be seen.

Dimensions: The holotype measures 1.94 mm in diameter and 1.69 mm in height.

Habitat: An infralittoral species which lives in gravel and cobble bottoms.

Distribution: Only known from the type locality.

Remarks: *Haplocochlias multiliratus* spec. nov. is a species very similar to *H. cyclophoreus* in its general shape, but different by the smaller size of shell and protoconch, larger number of spiral cordlets on the last half whorl and also because in this part the spaces between cords are narrower and the axial striae become grooves; also by the more open umbilicus with fine cordlets inside.

It differs from *H. lucasensis* and *H. compactus* by having strong axial striae in the interspaces between the cords over all the shell. From *H. risoneidenergyae* it may be distinguished by its smaller size and by the presence on the last half whorl of more of 50 spiral cordlets.

swifti group

Remarks: The species comprised in this group have a very thick and internally crenulated outer lip, the umbilicus

reduced to a small fissure and the periphery of the shell angled by the presence of thick and prominent spiral cords.

Haplocochlias swifti Vanatta, 1913 (Figures 9, 10)

Haplocochlias swifti Vanatta, 1913. *Proceedings of the Academy of Natural Sciences of Philadelphia*, 65: 23-24, fig. 3. [Type locality: St. Thomas, Virgin Islands].

Type material: Holotype in ANSP (10292).

Material examined: **USA:** 2 s, rocky reef, 45 m, Palm Beach, Florida (MCZ, 207094); 1 s, Off Palm Beach, Florida, 54 m (MCZ 226853). **Cuba:** 1 s, Cable Inglés, Cienfuegos, in sediment from 31 m depth (MHNS); 1 s, Bahía de Cienfuegos, 20-30 m (MHNS); 1 s, j, Rancho Luna Beach, Cienfuegos (MHNS).

Description: Original description in VANATTA (1913: 23-24): "Shell small, umbilicate, turbinata, white, suture deeply impressed, spire elevated, whorls 5, very convex, contabulate, the first whorl somewhat eroded, the two following whorls bicarinate, the penultimate and body whorl more or less tricarinate. The body whorl is sculptured with 24 spaced spiral striae with microscopic vertical striae in the interstices. The fourth, sixth and eighth striae below the suture on the body whorl are larger than the others and three or four striae near the umbilicus are closer together. The umbilicus is of moderate size. The aperture is orbicular, peristome continuous, very thick, and broadly reflexed, crenate, parietal callus

thick, columella narrow above and broad at the base, bearing a median groove.

Length 3.92, diameter 3.92 mm".

The protoconch (Fig. 9C, 10C), barely $\frac{3}{4}$ of whorl, is smooth and measures about 220 μ m. Ornamentation consists of spiral cords, axial ribs and microtubercles in the spaces between cords. First and second whorls of the teleoconch are bicarinate; third and last round to tricarinate. On the last whorl there are 24 spiral cords, of which the 4th, the 6th and 8th are more prominent. The spaces between cords (Figs. 9D, 10D-E) have fine axial ribs, slightly prosocline and regularly spaced, forming small quadrangular cells whose

Figure 9. *Haplocochlias swifti* Vanatta, 1913. A, B: adult shell, diameter 3.7 mm, Rancho Luna Beach, Cienfuegos, Cuba (MHNS); C: protoconch of this shell; D: microsculpture of the last whorl.

Figura 9. Haplocochlias swifti Vanatta, 1913. A, B: concha adulta, diámetro 3,7 mm, Playa Rancho Luna, Cienfuegos, Cuba (MHNS); C: protoconcha de la misma concha; D: microescultura de la última vuelta.

Figure 10. *Haplocochlias swifti* Vanatta, 1913. A, B: immature shell, diameter 1.6 mm in diameter, Rancho Luna Beach, Cienfuegos, Cuba (MHNS); C: protoconch of this shell; D, E: microsculpture of the last whorl and detail.

Figura 10. *Haplocochlias swifti* Vanatta, 1913. A, B: concha inmadura, diámetro 1,6 mm, Playa Rancho Luna, Cienfuegos, Cuba (MHNS); C: protoconcha de la misma concha; D, E: microescultura de la última vuelta y detalle.

surface is covered by microtubercles which cover neither the axial ribs nor the spiral cords. The umbilicus is limited to a narrow fissure. Aperture rounded; peristome continuous, very thick; columella and outer lip reflected outwards, inner aspect crenulated.

Dimensions: Large specimens can reach 6 mm in diameter.

Habitat: From 5 down to 45 m in depth (DE JONG & COOMANS, 1988). On a bottom of sand and coral gravel down to 45 m in depth (DÍAZ MERLANO & PUYANA HEGEDUS, 1994). In sandy/muddy bottoms to 4 m deep and near reefs at 8 m depth; in bottoms covered by a thin yellowish-tan layer of mucus from the corals (information of the material deposited in the UCR) (RODRÍGUEZ SEVILLA ET AL., 2003). In Cienfuegos, Cuba, it was found on a bottom of coralline sand to 31 m depth.

Distribution: Saint Thomas, Virgin Islands (VANATTA, 1913). Havana, Cuba (PILSBRY & AGUAYO, 1933). Bocas del Toro Is., Panamá (OLSSON & MCGINTY, 1958; ABBOTT, 1974). Fernando de Noronha (RÍOS, 1985). Curaçao and Bonaire (DE JONG & COOMANS, 1988). From the Greater Antilles and Panama to Brazil (DÍAZ MERLANO & PUYANA HEGEDUS 1994). Between Cahuita and Gandoca, Costa Rica (ESPINOSA & ORTEA, 2001).

Remarks: *H. swifti* was the first species of this genus to be described from the western Atlantic. The pho-

tographed specimen (Fig. 9A-B), 3.7 x 3.7 mm, has 5 spiral whorls and fully agrees with the description and original figuration.

VANATTA (1913) wrote: "This species differs from *Haplocochlias cyclophoreus* Carpenter, 1864 by having coarser spiral sculpture, by having a more reflexed lip, and by being umbilicate". We must bear in mind that *H. cyclophoreus* is a species of the American Pacific, that except for its conchological similarity, has little to do with *H. swifti*. The comparison drawn by these authors was based on it being the type species and only known congener.

ABBOTT (1974, n° 457) figured a shell of *H. moolenbeeki* as *H. swifti*.

RODRÍGUEZ, VARGAS & CORTÉS (2003) wrote: "the specimen mentioned by ROBINSON & MONTTOYA (1987) as *Haplocochlias swifti* is *H. costaricensis* (Robinson 1991)". However, the taxon *Haplocochlias costaricensis* is included by ROBINSON (1991) in his Doctoral dissertation "The systematics and paleoecology of the prosobranch gastropods of the Pleistocene Moín formation of Costa Rica", Tulane University, New Orleans, Louisiana. It is here considered an unavailable name due to lack of publication of this thesis. This taxon appears to have been cited only once, in RODRÍGUEZ SEVILLA ET AL. (2003), a publication dealing with the marine gastropod molluscs of the Caribbean coast of Costa Rica.

Haplocochlias onaneyi Espinosa, Ortea & Fernández-Garcés, 2005 (Figure 11)

Haplocochlias onaneyi Espinosa, Ortea & Fernández-Garcés, 2005. *Avicennia*, 17: 72, figs. 1A-C. [Type Locality: Alamar, Havana, Cuba].

Type material: Holotype of *H. onaneyi* in IES, CITMA, Havana.

Material examined: Cuba: 1 s, María la Gorda, Guanahacabibes, 31 m, coralline sand (MHNS).

Description: Original description of *H. onaneyi* in ESPINOSA, ORTEA & FERNÁNDEZ-GARCÉS (2005): "Concha robusta, de menor tamaño que *H. swifti*, de color blanco, espira formada por 4 vueltas de rápido crecimiento. Protoconcha con 3/4 de vuelta de espira, tiene 3 cordoncillos espira-

les y mide 237 µm de diámetro y presenta una gruesa variz labial. Teleoconcha formada por 3 1/4 vueltas, ornamentada con cordones espirales y estrías axiales y micropits en los espacios entre cordones. Se observan 2 cordones en la primera vuelta, 4 en la segunda y 18-19 cordones es la última. Las

Figure 11. *Haplocochlias onaneyi* Espinosa, Ortea & Fernández-Garcés, 2005. A, B: shell, diameter 1.93 mm, María la Gorda, Guanahacabibes, Cuba (MHNS); C, D: protoconch of this shell; E-F: microsculpture of the last whorl.

Figura 11. *Haplocochlias onaneyi* Espinosa, Ortea & Fernández-Garcés, 2005. A, B: concha, diámetro 1,93 mm, María la Gorda, Guanahacabibes, Cuba (MHNS); C, D: protoconcha de la misma concha; E-F: microescultura de la última vuelta.

estriás espirales en la primera vuelta forman celdillas cuadrangulares, en la segunda y última vuelta, las estriás se vuelven más numerosas y las celdillas tienen forma rectangular, y el espacio que delimitan aparece totalmente cubierto por micropits. Ombligo estrecho, profundo, ligeramente ocluido por la reflexión de la columela, hacia su interior penetran 2-3 cordoncillos. Abertura redondeada, peristoma continuo; labio externo muy grueso, frontalmente ensanchado, con crenulaciones (de 2 en 2) en su interior; la columela se ensancha hacia su base y se refleja exteriormente formando un ángulo característico; zona parietal cubierta por una delgada capa callosa”.

Shell robust, smaller in size than *H. swifti*, white in colour, spire formed by 4 rapidly expanding whorls. Protoconch 3/4 whorls, with 3 spiral cordlets, measuring about 240 μm in diameter, and having thick lip varix. Teleoconch composed of 3 1/4 whorls, ornamented by spiral cords and axial grooves with micropits in the spaces between them. There are 2 cords in the first whorl, 4 in the second and 18-19 cords in the last one. The spiral grooves on the first whorls form irregular cells, and on the second and the last whorl, the cells become more numerous and rectangular in shape, while the delimited space appears completely covered by microtubercles. Umbilicus narrow, deep, slightly occluded by the reflection of the columella, and with 2-3 cordlets penetrating towards its interior. Aperture rounded, continuous peristome; outer lip very thick, frontally expanded, with denticulations inside (by pairs); the

columella widens towards its base and is reflected outwardly forming a characteristic angle; parietal area covered by a thin layer of callus.

Dimensions: Maximum reported size: 2.1 mm. The studied specimen measures 1.93 mm in height and 1.91 mm in maximum diameter.

Habitat: The holotype of *C. onaneyi* was found alive in Alamar, Havana, Cuba, inside a small cave at 17 m depth. The other 2 shells found (paratypes) come from sandy sediment collected at Rancho Luna Beach, Cienfuegos, at 54 m, and at Playa Varadero, Matanzas, at 15 m. The photographed specimen was found in sediment from a coralline sand bottom at 30 m depth at María la Gorda (West Cuba).

Distribution: Cuba: North Havana, North Matanzas, Cienfuegos Provinces (ESPINOSA, ORTEA & FERNÁNDEZ-GARCÉS, 2005).

Remarks: ESPINOSA, ORTEA, FERNÁNDEZ-GARCÉS & MORO (2007, fig. 006) refigured *H. onaneyi* showing a better depiction of the original apertural view.

ROSENBERG (2013) indicates that from the figures, *H. onaneyi* seems to be a synonym of *H. williami*. However, after carefully examining the illustrations of *H. williami*, in our opinion, it is not the same species: the periphery of the shell is strongly angled, forming a characteristic shoulder; also the latter differs in the number of spiral cords. *H. onaneyi* may be distinguished from the other species of the group by the number of spiral cords of the last whorl and the characteristic aperture.

Haplocochlias garciai spec. nov. (Figure 12)

Type material: Holotype deposited in USNM (1 s, ex-CEG).

Type locality: East side entrance to Caribe Point Bight, S. Roatán Island, Honduras, under rubble in 0.7 m (CEG).

Etymology: The species is named after Emilio García, who provided the shell for study.

Description: Shell turbiniform, robust, spire formed by 4 1/4 rapidly expanding whorls. The protoconch has 3/4 whorls, measures about 210 μm in diameter and has 4 spiral cords. Teleoconch formed by 3 1/2 whorls, totally

covered by thick spiral cords. In apertural view, two cords can be seen on the first whorl, 5 on the second and 17 on the last. On the last whorl, the 3rd, 5th and 6th cords are the most prominent, forming slight angles on the periphery

Figura 12. *Haplocochlias garciai* spec. nov. A, B: holotype, height 2.18 mm, S. Roatán Island, Honduras (USNM); C: protoconch; D: microsculpture from last whorl.

Figura 12. *Haplocochlias garciai* spec. nov. A, B: holotipo, altura 2,18 mm, sur de la isla de Roatán, Honduras (USNM); C: protoconcha; D: microescultura de la última vuelta.

of the shell. In the interspaces between the cords striae are distributed more or less regularly, forming rectangular cells whose surface is covered by microtubercles. Aperture circular, prosocline; outer lip very thick, widened frontally and strongly crenulated in its inner margin. The external thickening of the lip is very

evident. Columella slightly sloping, triangular in shape, with a central groove, forming a rounded corner in its confluence with the outer lip. Umbilicus reduced to a narrow fissure, two fine cordlets penetrating inside.

Dimensions: The holotype measures 2.18 mm in height and 2.00 mm in diameter.

Habitat: Infralittoral species living under rubble in about ½ m deep.

Distribution: Only known from the type locality.

Remarks: *H. garciai* spec. nov. differs from the remaining species of the group by having the largest number of cordlets on the protoconch, a smaller number of cords in the teleoconch and by the shape of the lip.

From *H. swifti*, it can be distinguished by the lesser number of spiral cords and the denticles of the outer lip, which are wider. From *H. onaneyi* by the smaller diameter of the protoconch and the different shape of the denticles of the outer lip. From *H. minusdentatus* spec. nov. and *H. loperi* spec. nov. by the smaller diameter of the protoconch and the different shape of the denticles of the outer lip.

Haplocochlias williami Barros, Santos, Santos, Cabral & Acioli, 2002

Haplocochlias williami Barros, Santos, Santos, Cabral & Acioli, 2002. *Boletim Técnico Científico do CEPENE* 10 (1): 45. [Type locality: Fernando de Noronha, Brazil].

Type material: Type material of *H. williami* in Museu de Malacologia da UFRPE (n° 7601.5). Not examined.

Other material examined: None.

Description: Original description of *H. williami* in BARROS ET AL. (2002: 45): “Concha pequena, turbinada, protoconcha formada por uma volta convexa e de aspecto liso, núcleo emerso, liso, posicionado no topo da espira. Espira mediana, correspondendo aproximadamente a 45% do CT da concha, ornada por várias cordas espirais fortes e dois ombros evidentes. Fenda umbilical parcialmente fechada. Linhas de crescimento evidentes nos espaços entre as cordas e as costelas, formando um fino retículo. Abertura circular, amplamente expandida com o hesteróstoma pouco refletido; lábio externo espesso marcado ventralmente e lateralmente por pregas macroscópicas. Região posterior do lábio externo afilada coincidindo com o início da forte região parietal, a qual é pouco extensa e levemente refletida sobre a parede umbilical. Base cônica não perfurada, delimitada interiormente por uma forte corda umbilical. Anfractos angulosos, sobretudo os espirais; a primeira volta da teleoconcha ornada apenas por dois ombros; espirais cruzados por linhas

de crescimento microscópicas; linhas axiais microscópicas, que nesta região não estão restritas aos espaços, se estendendo de sutura a sutura”.

Maximum reported size: 2.1 mm.

Habitat: In Brazil, *H. williami* was collected in sediments from grit bottom at 54 meters in depth.

Distribution: Brazil: Fernando de Noronha (BARROS ET AL., 2002).

Remarks: ROSENBERG (2013) stated that from the figures *H. onaneyi* seems to be a synonym of *H. williami*. On this synonymy see remarks under *H. onaneyi*. We regret not being able to present a figure of this species, from which only the holotype is known. The original figure is rather deficient; furthermore, the description is not very detailed. Under these conditions the identification of the species is very difficult. We have tried to borrow the holotype or find a similar shell, but our efforts were not successful.

Haplocochlias minusdentatus spec. nov. Rubio, Rolán & Redfern (Figure 13)

Haplocochlias sp. B. Redfern, 2001: 16, fig. 67; Redfern, 2013: 21, figs. 68A-B.

Type material: Holotype in FLMNH (464796) and 1 paratype in FLMNH (464796); other paratype in BMSM (52542).

Figure 13. *Haplocochlias minusdentatus* spec. nov. A, B: holotype, 1.25 × 1.05 mm, Abaco Island, Bahamas (FLMNH); C: detail of the varicose outer lip; D: protoconch; E, F: microsculpture of the last whorl.

Figura 13. *Haplocochlias minusdentatus* spec. nov. A, B: *holotipo*, 1,25 × 1,05 mm, isla de Abaco, Bahamas (FLMNH); C: *detalle del labio externo varicoso*; D: *protoconcha*; E, F: *microescultura de la última vuelta*.

Other material examined: None.

Type locality: Abaco Island, Bahamas, 7 m.

Etymology: The name makes reference to its small size and the depressed denticles on the inner part of the outer lip.

Description: Shell very small, white in colour, with a spire formed by 3 1/4 rapidly expanding whorls. The protoconch has 3/4 whorls and measures about 250 μm in diameter, having 2-3 thin spiral cords. Teleoconch with 2 1/2 whorls, ornamented with strong spiral cords, prosocline axial striae in the spaces between the cords, and microtubercles. On the first whorl there are 4 spiral cords and 12-13 cords in the last one; the more pronounced of them are placed at the periphery, producing a slight angulation of the shell. The axial striae on the first whorls of the teleoconch form quadrangular spaces which become rectangular on the last one. Aperture rounded, prosocline, peristome continuous; outer lip and columella thick and reflected outwards; on the inner part of the outer lip faint, wide, and well-spaced crenulations can be seen; the columella is straight, basally wider forming an angular area, at the intersection of the umbilical cord and the outer lip. Umbilicus small, partially occluded by the reflection of the columella, inside there are 2-3 spiral threads. The outer margin of the outer lip forms a characteristic thickening similar to that of some species of the genus *Nassarius* (Nassariidae).

Dimensions: The holotype measures 1.25 mm in height and 1.05 mm in diameter.

Habitat: The photographed shell was collected from a coralline bottom at 7 m; the other two specimens were collected in a similar type of bottom between 6 m and 52 m.

Distribution: Only known from Abaco, Bahamas, its type locality.

Remarks: This is the smallest species of the group, 1.25 mm in height and 1.05 mm in diameter; in spite of this, it is the species with one of the largest protoconchs (250 μm in maximum diameter).

Haplocochlias minusdentatus spec. nov. can be distinguished from other species of the group (*H. swifti*, *H. onaneyi* and *H. garciai* spec. nov.) by its small size, fewer spiral whorls on the first and on the last whorl and a larger protoconch. From *H. loperi* it can be distinguished by having a greater number of spiral cords on the first whorl of the teleoconch.

Because of its size it might give the impression that it is a juvenile of another species, but the lip thickening and dilatation, and the weak crenulations on the interior of the outer umbilicus strongly suggest an adult stage. The other two specimens are of similar size and lip morphology, indicating that they are also adults.

Haplocochlias loperi spec. nov. Rubio, Rolán & Lee (Figure 14)

Type material: Holotype (FLMNH 457010) and two paratypes (FLMNH 457011), coll. M. Loper, November 2003.

Type locality: The G. Spot, French Cay, 18 m, Turks & Caicos Islands.

Etymology: Named for its collector, Dr. Michael Loper, a physician in Jacksonville, Florida.

Description: Shell very small, turbinate, with a robust appearance, as wide as high (H/D: 1.02), spire formed by 3 rapidly expanding whorls. The protoconch 3/4 of whorl, measuring about 260 μm and with three thick spiral cords and a thickened lip varix.

The teleoconch has 2 1/4 whorls ornamented by thick, prominent spiral cords, axial grooves and microtubercles. In apertural view there are 3 spiral cords on the first whorl and 11 cords on the last one. The cords are narrower than the interspaces. The

Figure 14. *Haplocochlias loperi* spec. nov. A: holotype, height 1.29 mm, Turks & Caicos (FLMNH); B: paratype (FLMNH); C: protoconch of the other paratype.

Figura 14. *Haplocochlias loperi* spec. nov. A: holotipo, altura 1,29 mm, Turks & Caicos (FLMNH); B: paratipo (FLMNH); C: protoconcha del otro paratipo.

axial striae are strong, somewhat prosocline, are regularly spaced and occupy all of the space between cords, which is slightly concave; at the crossing point with the cords small irregular nodules form as rectangular cells completely covered by microtubercles. Aperture rounded, prosocline, peristome continuous; outer lip thickened and frontally expanded, showing weak, long, wide denticles on its inner

basal aspect; parietal area covered by a thin callous coat; columella straight, very wide at its base, scarcely reflected. Umbilicus small, partially covered by the parietal reflection, on its inner wall there are thin growth lines and two spiral cordlets.

Dimensions: The holotype is 1.29 mm in height and 1.26 mm in maximum diameter.

Habitat: Unknown.

Distribution: Known only from the type locality.

Haplocochlias loperi spec. nov. differs from its congeners, *H. garciai* spec. nov., *H. onaneyi* and *H. swifti*, by its smaller size, the size of the protoconch (260 μm , one of the larger in the genus), by the small number of spiral cords, the prominent form of these and the concavity of the

spaces between cords. The closest species (due to its size) is *H. minusdentatus*, which differs in the teleoconch spiral sculpture, having 3 cords on the first whorl instead of four and by the thickness of the cords of the protoconch. From *H. bieleri* spec. nov. it differs in the small number of spiral cords and the different shape of the denticulations inside the outer lip.

Haplocochlias bieleri spec. nov. (Figures 15, 16)

Type material: Holotype (Figs. 15A-B) in FMNH (333880). Paratypes: 6 in FMNH (333878, 333879, 288220, 333896) from close areas in Florida, Monroe County, USA).

Type locality: Florida, Monroe County, Sta. FK-202, Molasses Reef, Upper Florida Keys, USA, 25° 00' 33"N, 080° 22' 35"W, 7 m deep.

Etymology: Named for its collector, Dr. Rüdiger Bieler, Curator, Division of Invertebrates, Field Museum, Chicago.

Description: Shell very small, turbiniform, strong and robust, higher than wide (H/D: 1.20) with spire formed by 3 $\frac{1}{2}$ quickly increasing whorls. The protoconch has $\frac{3}{4}$ whorl, measuring 230 μm and on it three strong cords can be seen as well as the varix of a thickened lip. The teleoconch has 2 $\frac{3}{4}$ whorls and its ornamentation is formed by strong spiral cords, some very prominent, axial striae and microtubercles. In apertural view 2 spiral cords can be seen on the first whorl, 3 cords on the second and 25 cords on the last one; in each whorl there are two very prominent cords which make the profile angulate. The interspaces between cords are of similar size in the sutural and peripheral areas, but in the base they become narrower and closer set. If the holotype is observed in apical view it can be seen that in the last $\frac{1}{2}$ whorl, between the spiral cords, new cordlets are formed, which increase in the proximity of the external lip, of equal size and also with spaces between cords. The axial striae are somewhat prosocline, on the first whorl they are more separate forming quadrangular spaces totally covered by microtubercles; on the subsequent whorls the striae are more numerous and closer. Aperture rounded, prosocline, peristome continuous; external lip very wide and expanded frontally, and

inside elongated and irregular denticles can be seen, which are extended from the external margin towards the inside, grouped by two. The columella is almost straight and is widened towards the base, it is very wide and is reflected towards the umbilicus, which is occluded almost entirely; the parietal area is covered by a strong coat.

Dimensions: the holotype is 1.56 mm in height and 1.30 mm in maximum diameter (H/D: 1.20).

Habitat: The type material was collected in a reef with sandy patches, at 7 metres.

Distribution: Known only from the type locality.

Remarks: The main morphological character which differentiates *H. bieleri* from the other species of the genus, is the presence of the two spiral cords per whorl which are projected as carinae over the others, form an angle on the shell and give it a characteristic profile. Other differential characters are the shape of the shell, the number of spiral cords and their greater concentration in the basal area, the shape of the external lip, columella and umbilicus, practical occluded by the reflection of the columella. If we observe a specimen of *H. bieleri* not totally adult (Figs. 15D), we can see that the two peripheral carinae per whorl are invariable; however, the

Figure 15. *Haplocochlias bieleri* spec. nov. A, B: holotype, 1.56 × 1.3 mm, Florida, USA (FMNH); C, D: paratype, 1.2 × 1.25 mm; E: detail of the aperture and columellar area of the holotype (FMNH).

Figura 15. *Haplocochlias bieleri* spec. nov. A, B: holotipo, 1,56 × 1,3 mm Florida, EE.UU. (FMNH); C, D: paratipo, 1,2 × 1,25 mm; E: detalle de la abertura y del área columelar del holotipo (FMNH).

Figure 16. *Haplocochlias bieleri* spec. nov. A: protoconch of a paratype; B, C: microsculpture of the last whorl.

Figura 16. *Haplocochlias bieleri* spec. nov. A: protoconcha de un paratipo; B, C: microescultura de la última vuelta.

number of spiral cords decrease drastically (15 on the last whorl), the external lip is not totally expanded, the denticles inside the external lip can be seen clearly and the columella does not occlude the umbilicus which is shown as a small fissure. These morphological differences between the adult and the non-adult specimens could incorrectly lead to the description of new species. The closer species by its general shape and dimensions is *H. minusdentata*, from which it can be distinguished by the larger number of the spiral cords and their shape, by the shape and number of the denticles of the external lip and by the umbilicus almost occluded. From

the general shape and the denticulation of the external lip, the closest species is *H. onaneyi*, from which it can be distinguished by its smaller size, larger number of spiral cords, two peripheral carinae by whorl and the umbilicus almost totally closed by the reflection of the columella.

H. bieleri spec. nov. differs from *H. garciai* spec. nov. and *H. swifti* mainly by its small size (<1.6 mm), from *H. williami* by the larger number of spiral cords, and from *H. loperi* it is distinguished furthermore by its umbilicus being practically closed, by the different shape of the labial denticles and the larger number of spiral cords.

ortizi group

Remarks: The main characteristics of the species which form this group is having the shape of a spinning top, the very numerous axial striae, and the

straight columella widened at its base, which angles the aperture at its intersection with the outer lip and the umbilical cord.

Haplocochlias ortizi Espinosa, Ortea & Fernández-Garcés, 2005 (Figures 17, 18)

Haplocochlias ortizi Espinosa, Ortea & Fernández-Garcés, 2005b. *Avicennia* 17: 73, figs. 1D-F. [Type locality: Rancho Luna Beach, Cienfuegos, Cuba, 54 m].

Type material: Holotype in IES, CITMA, Havana, Cuba. Paratypes in MNCN, Madrid; MNH of Santa Cruz de Tenerife and MHN "Carlos de la Torre" of Holguín, Cuba.

Material examined: Cuba: 3 s, Rancho Luna Beach, 10-20 m; 3 s, Rancho Luna Beach, 30 m; 15 s, Rancho Luna Beach, coralline sediments, 40 m; 4 s, Rancho Luna Beach, 45 m; 2 s, Punta de Tamarindo, 56 m; 2 s, Faro Colorados, 36 m; 1 s, Havana, 15 m.

Description: Original description in ESPINOSA ET AL. (2005): *Concha de tamaño pequeño, turbiniforme, de color blanco leche y escultura espiral muy marcada. Protoconcha de 0.5 vueltas lisas y brillantes, sin escultura notable. Teleoconcha de unas 3,3 a 3,5 vueltas, escultradas con fuertes costillas espirales, entre las que hay líneas axiales de crecimiento, presentes desde el comienzo de la teleoconcha hasta el final de la última vuelta. Ombligo estrecho. La abertura es circular, reforzada por un fuerte peristoma engrosado en su cara externa, frontalmente aplanado y sin escultura, con una prolongación notable hacia la base de la concha*". We add: Protoconch $\frac{3}{4}$ whorl, about 230 μm in diameter, smooth surface with 3 spiral cordlets and a thick lip varix. The teleoconch has 3 $\frac{3}{4}$ whorls. Sculpture of thick spiral cords, and the interspaces between cords covered by fine closely-packed axial procline grooves. On the first whorl there are 2 spiral cords, 3 in the second, and 15-20 on the last one; of the latter, the first five are distributed between the sutures and, are more prominent at the periphery and their interspaces are unequal; the cords which are distributed towards the base are sized more regularly, as are their interspaces. After the first whorl of the teleoconch numerous axial striae appear between cords, replacing the cells and the microtubercles. On the last half whorl, between the

spiral cords other finer ones appear, giving the appearance that the cords are double.

The aperture is rounded; at the confluence of the columella and the outer lip, an angulation is formed, extending outwards and as well as partially occluding the umbilicus, which is narrow, delimited by a thick cord; inside there are 2-3 thin cordlets.

Maximum reported size: 3 mm. The shell figured measures 2.7 mm in height.

Habitat: The type material was found in sediments from coralline sandy bottom at 54 m. The other material examined is from sediments collected at 40 m.

Distribution: Only known from Rancho Luna Beach, Cienfuegos, Cuba, the type locality.

Remarks: ESPINOSA ET AL. (2005: 72) reported: "*Haplocochlias ortizi*, especie nueva, difiere de *H. onaneyi* (= *williamii*) por ser de tamaño algo mayor, carecer de escultura espiral en la protoconcha y por tener las líneas axiales intercostales de crecimiento más finas. De *H. swifti* se diferencia por ser de tamaño menor, tener ombligo y carecer de escultura en la cara frontal del peristoma. *H. moolenbeeki* es una especie de tamaño mayor, ampliamente umbilicada y de peristoma poco engrosado".

Likewise, in the original description the authors mention that the protoconch

Figure 17. *Haplocochlias ortizi* Espinosa, Ortea & Fernández-Garcés, 2005. A, B: adult shell, 2.1 × 2.7 mm, Rancho Luna Beach, Cienfuegos, Cuba (MHNS); C: protoconch, same shell as B; D, E: microsculpture and detail of the last whorl.

Figura 17. *Haplocochlias ortizi* Espinosa, Ortea & Fernández-Garcés, 2005. A, B: concha adulta, 2,1 × 2,7 mm, Playa Rancho Luna, Cienfuegos, Cuba (MHNS); C: protoconcha, misma concha que B; D, E: microescultura y detalle de la última vuelta.

Figure 18. *Haplocochlias ortizi* Espinosa, Ortea & Fernández-Garcés, 2005. A: juvenile shell, diameter 1.5 mm, Rancho Luna Beach, Cienfuegos, Cuba (MHNS); B: protoconch of the same shell; C, D: microsculpture of the last whorl.

Figura 18. Haplocochlias ortizi Espinosa, Ortea & Fernández-Garcés, 2005. A: concha juvenil, diámetro 1,5 mm, Playa Rancho Luna, Cienfuegos, Cuba (MHNS); B: protoconcha de la misma concha; C, D: microscultura de la última vuelta.

is smooth, but photographs of shells from the type locality (Fig. 17C) show that they have some oblique cords.

The differential characters of this species are: the axial sculpture with very

dense and close vertical lamellae in the interspaces between the cords, the non-crenulated labial thickening and the columella being reflected outward along its entire length.

Haplocochlias densistriatus spec. nov. Rubio, Rolán & Lee (Figure 19)

Type material: Holotype in FLMNH (457015). Paratypes in FLMNH (457014, 1 s and 457016, 1 s) and in CHL (1 s).

Other material examined: Bahamas Islands: 3 s, off W side Cape Eleuthera, Eleuthera, 29 m, base of reef wall (CHL); 3 s, Long Cay Mooring, Long Cay, 23 m, hole in reef (CHL).

Type locality: Cape Eleuthera, Eleuthera, Bahamas Islands, 29 m.

Etymology: The specific name refers to the density of the axial striae.

Description: Shell small, turbiniform, with a conspicuous spire formed by slightly more than 4 rapidly expanding whorls. The protoconch 3/4 whorl, measuring 220 μm and having 3 very distinct spiral cordlets. The teleoconch consists of 3 1/2 whorls, ornamented with spiral cords and axial grooves, and microtubercles in their interspaces. The cords are narrower than their interspaces and number 2 on the first and second whorls and 9 on the last. On the first whorl of the teleoconch, the axial striae are more separated, forming quadrangular spaces; on the second whorl the axial grooves become more numerous, getting progressively closer together to form fine elongate lamellae which imparts a fine and elegant appearance to the teleoconch. Umbilicus broad and deep, delimited by a thick spiral cord, and towards its inner part the axial lamellae penetrate, but no spiral cordlets are observed. Aperture rounded, peristome continuous; outer

lip very thick and widened frontally, without crenulations inside; parietal area covered by a thin callous coat; columella almost straight, widened at its base and reflected outward, forming a widening at the intersection with the umbilical cord and the outer lip.

Dimensions: holotype 1.97 mm in height and 2.19 mm in diameter. The largest of the examined specimens measured 2.15 mm in height and 2.37 mm in diameter.

Habitat: Between 25 and 30 m, at the base of the reef.

Distribution: Only known from Cape Eleuthera and Long Cay Mooring, Bahamas Islands.

Remarks: *Haplocochlias densistriatus* spec. nov. can be distinguished from *H. ortizi* because the latter has fewer spiral cords, the interspaces between the cords are larger, the axial sculpture is formed by a larger number of elongate lamellae, and it has a wider umbilicus.

cubensis group

Remarks: The main characteristic of this group of species is that the adult

shell develops an outer lip which is frontally extended but not very thick.

Haplocochlias cubensis Espinosa, Ortea & Fernández-Garcés, 2007 (Figure 20)

Haplocochlias cubensis Espinosa, Ortea & Fernández-Garcés in Espinosa, Ortea, Fernández-Garcés & Moro, 2007. *Avicennia*, 19: 64-65, fig. 4. [Type locality: diving site Yemayá, María la Gorda, Guanahacabibes, Pinar del Río, Cuba, 30-40 m].

Figure 19. *Haplocochlias densistriatus* spec. nov. A: holotipo, diámetro 2.19 mm, Cape Eleuthera, Eleuthera, Bahamas (FLMNH); B: paratipo, diámetro 1.6 mm, same locality (FLMNH); C: paratipo, diámetro 2.35 mm, Long Cay Mooring, Long Cay, Bahamas (CHL); D: protoconch, same shell as B; E, F: microsculpture and detail of the last whorl.

Figura 19. *Haplocochlias densistriatus* spec. nov. A: holotipo, diámetro 2,19 mm, Cabo Eleuthera, Eleuthera, Bahamas (FLMNH); B: paratipo, diámetro 1,6 mm, misma localidad (FLMNH); C: paratipo, diámetro 2,35 mm, Long Cay Mooring, Long Cay, Bahamas (CHL); D: protoconcha, misma concha que B; E, F: microescultura y detalle de la última vuelta.

Type material: Holotype in the IES, Havana, Cuba. Two paratypes in the Museo de Ciencias Naturales de Tenerife, Canary Islands. Paratype in the collection of the second author (RFG), examined.

Other material examined: 5 s, María la Gorda, Guanahacabibes, Pinar del Río, Cuba, 30-40 m (MHNS).

Description: Original description in ESPINOSA, ORTEA, FERNÁNDEZ-GARCÉS & MORO (2007): “*Concha pequeña, turbini-forme, de color blanco hialino, con 4 ½ vueltas de las cuales la primera, decorada por dos hilos espirales, es de protoconcha. La teleoconcha está formada por 3 ½ vueltas, la primera decorada por tres cordones espirales entre los que hay laminillas axiales prosoclinas de crecimiento, regularmente separadas; hacia el final de la segunda vuelta hay unos 8 cordones espirales, con semejantes costillitas intercaladas; hacia el final de la penúltima vuelta hay unos 22 cordones. Al final de la última vuelta hay 72 cordones espirales, contando los 5 en el interior del ombligo. Abertura circular, engrosada solamente en la base, donde hay una prolongación por efecto de la terminación del cordón que limita el ombligo. Peristoma poco engrosado, crenulado por la terminación de los finos cordones espirales*”.

We add: The protoconch has $\frac{3}{4}$ whorl, measures 240 μm in maximum diameter, has a slightly granular surface and has 3 spiral cordlets. A thick varix marks the transition to the teleoconch, which has $3\frac{1}{2}$ spiral whorls. The $2\frac{1}{4}$ first whorls display prosocline axial striae between the spiral cords, forming cells that are covered by microtubercles. On the $1\frac{1}{4}$ remaining whorls the axial striae disappear, while the spiral cords are covered by microtubercles. The last whorl presents 70-75 crowded spiral cordlets, including those inside the umbilicus; which has a rounded periphery. The aperture is nearly circular; the

columella is slightly reflected outwards and the outer lip is crenulated due to the presence of the spiral cords. The umbilicus is narrow, partially occluded by the reflection of the columella; no periumbilical cord is observed.

Dimensions: The figured specimen is 2.65 mm in diameter and 2.51 mm in height (H/D: 0.95). Maximum reported size: 3 mm.

Habitat: Collected in coralline bottoms, 30-40 m (ESPINOSA, ORTEA, FERNÁNDEZ-GARCÉS & MORO, 2007).

Distribution: Only known from María la Gorda, Guanahacabibes, Pinar del Río, Cuba, its type locality.

Remarks: ESPINOSA ET AL. (2007) in relation to the protoconch mention: “... con $4\frac{1}{2}$ vueltas de las cuales la primera, decorada por 2 hilos espirales, es de protoconcha”. However, as can be seen (Fig. 20C), the protoconch has 3 spiral cordlets, like other species of the genus.

Haplocochlias cubensis is primarily characterized by the great number of spiral cords on the last whorl, about 72 (including 5 located in the inner part of the umbilicus), with a laminar appearance, produced by deep grooves between them, the lack of axial sculpture, and the presence of microtubercles on the cords. It differs from the remaining species in the genus by its rounded periphery, by the great number of spiral cords on the last whorl, by the absence of keels, the absence of axial grooves in the final $\frac{1}{4}$ whorl and its crenulated, not thickened, lip.

Haplocochlias arrondoi spec. nov. (Figures 1, 21, 22)

Type material: Holotype (Fig. 21A) deposited in MNCN (15.05/60043). Paratypes in the following: MNHN (IM -2012-2530, 1 s, Fig. 21B), MHNS (100577, 1 s, Fig. 21C), MCZ (377778, 1 s, Fig. 21D, 22A), FLMNH (457013, 1 s, Fig. 21E) all from Rancho Luna Beach, Cuba; IES (1 s, Fig. 21F) from Faro de los Colorados, Cienfuegos, Cuba; collection of E. Arrondo (1 s).

Other material examined: Cuba: 8 s, Cienfuegos Bay, 35 m (MHNS); 8 s, Rancho Luna Beach, 10-20 m (MHNS); 6 s, Rancho Luna Beach, 30 m (MHNS); 8 s, Rancho Luna Beach, 35 m (MHNS); 4 s,

Figure 20. *Haplocochlias cubensis* Espinosa, Ortea & Fernández-Garcés, 2007. A, B: shell, diameter 2.65 mm, María la Gorda, Guanahacabibes, Cuba (MHNS); C: protoconch of the same shell; D, E: microsculpture of the last whorl.

Figura 20. Haplocochlias cubensis Espinosa, Ortea & Fernández-Garcés, 2007. A, B: concha, diámetro 2,65 mm, María la Gorda, Guanahacabibes, Cuba (MHNS); C: protoconcha de la misma concha; D, E: microescultura de la última vuelta.

Rancho Luna Beach, 40 m (MHNS); 8 s, Rancho Luna Beach, 45 m (MHNS); 5 s, Faro Colorados, 35 m (MHNS); 4 s, Faro Colorados, 56 m (MHNS); 2 s, Punta Tamarindo, 56 m (MHNS); 1 s, Los Laberintos, 35 m (MHNS).

Type locality: Rancho Luna Beach, Cienfuegos, Cuba, 30-40 m.

Etymology: The name is after the malacologist Ernesto Arrondo Odriozola, from Donostia, Spain.

Description: Shell very small, turbiniform, as high as wide (H/D: 1), spire formed by 3½ whorls separated by a wide and deep suture. The protoconch has ¾ whorls, measuring about 240 µm in diameter, smooth except for 3 spiral cordlets which run through it. Teleoconch formed by 3¼ whorls, rounded, slightly angled on the periphery in its dorsal area by three spiral cords somewhat higher than others. Ornamentation consisting of spiral cords, fine axial grooves in the spaces between them and microtubercles distributed between the axial striae. Cords are fairly uniform in size as are their interspaces, and the axial striae are regularly distributed throughout the teleoconch. On the first whorl there are 3-4 spiral cords; 8 in the second, and 32 on the last; of these the 2nd, but especially the 5th and 8th are the highest and stand out on the periphery as small keels. On the last half-whorl, the suture becomes broad and deep, axial striae disappear, and fine spiral cordlets appear in the interspaces in the area near the outer lip so that one loses count of the total number of cords. Aperture rounded, peristome continuous, barely attached; both the outer and inner lips appear frontally expanded without denticulation or apparent crenulations; just at the point of union between the inner lip, the outer lip and the umbilical cord an expansion and a small angulation are formed. Base slightly concave. Umbilicus narrow, deep, not modified or occluded; it is delimited by a strong spiral cord; on its inner part 2-3 fine cordlets can be observed.

Operculum multispiral with a central nucleus.

Radula formula N.5.1.5.N. The radicularian tooth is broad (not as much as *H. cyclophoreus*, type species of the genus). The laterals are well developed and are similar in size and shape; they present a characteristic bend in the shaft and cusps with finely serrated margins (outer and inner). There is a latero-mar-

ginal plate fused to the first marginal tooth shaft. The marginal teeth are the same shape, with long, narrow and strongly overhanging cusps, strongly curved outward.

Dimensions: Holotype: 2.13 mm in height and 2.17 mm in diameter (H/D=0.98); paratype (MHNS): 1.66 mm in height and 1.66 mm in diameter (H/D=1.00); Faro de los Colorados: (paratype in IES) 2.41 mm in diameter and 2.2 mm in height (H/D: 0.91); the largest shell (paratype in MCZ) examined measured 1.75 mm in diameter.

Habitat: Frequently found in sediments taken from coralline sand bottom between 15 and 50 m in depth.

Distribution: Rancho Luna Beach and Faro los Colorados, Cienfuegos, Cuba.

Remarks: We have seen a remarkable morphological difference between fully adult individuals which have developed the frontally expanded lip and individuals that being slightly sub-adult still have not developed it, as can be seen in the photographed samples from Rancho Luna (Figs. 21C-E): the outer lip first has a sharp border, slightly-denticulate by the presence of spiral cords; parietal area of the inner lip without callus, reduced to a thin lamella; the columella is curved at the beginning, then becomes deflected, widens towards its base and forms an angle at the point of junction with the umbilical cord and the outer lip.

Haplocochlias arrondoii spec. nov. may be distinguished from the other species with a spirally-corded protoconch by the presence on the teleoconch of 2 more elevated spiral cords forming a sort of keel which angulates the shell giving it a characteristic profile, by the number of cords on the last whorl, and by the development in fully adult shells of a frontally expanded lip, which is neither denticulate nor crenulated. *Haplocochlias cubensis* has a greater number of spiral cords on the last teleoconch whorls and

Figure 21. *Haplocochlias arrondoi* spec. nov. A: holotype, diameter 2.17 mm (MNCN); B: paratype, diameter 1.9 mm (MNHN); C: paratype, diameter 1.66 mm (MHNS); D: paratype, diameter 1.75 mm (MCZ); E: paratype, diameter 2.1 mm (FMNH), all from Rancho Luna Beach, Cienfuegos, Cuba; F: paratype, diameter 2.41 mm (IES), Faro Colorados, Cienfuegos, Cuba.

Figura 21. Haplocochlias arrondoi spec. nov. A: *holotipo*, diámetro 2,17 mm (MNCN); B: *paratipo*, diámetro 1,9 mm (MNHN); C: *paratipo*, diámetro 1,66 mm (MHNS); D: *paratipo*, diámetro 1,75 mm (MCZ); E: *paratipo*, diámetro 2,1 mm (FMNH), todos de Playa Rancho Luna, Cienfuegos, Cuba; F: *paratipo*, diámetro 2,41 mm (IES), Faro Colorados, Cienfuegos, Cuba.

Figure 22. *Haplocochlias arrondoii* spec. nov. A: apex and protoconch of a paratype from MCZ; B: apex and protoconch of another shell (MHNS); C, E: microsculpture and detail of the last whorl.

Figura 22. *Haplocochlias arrondoii* spec. nov. A: ápice y protoconcha de un paratipo de MCZ; B: ápice y protoconcha de otra concha (MHNS); C, E: microescultura y detalle de la última vuelta.

lacks axial striae between cords. *H. harryleei* spec. nov. has a round periphery and a greater protoconch diameter.

The radula (Figs. 1A-B) differs from that figured by HICKMAN & MCLEAN

(1990: 144, fig. 97B) for *H. cyclophoreus*, the type species of the genus, by having the central tooth narrower and the edge of the lateral teeth with finely serrated margins.

Haplocochlias harryleei spec. nov. (Figure 23)

Type material: Holotype deposited in FLMNH (457012).

Other material examined: None.

Type locality: Off Isla Escudo de Veraguas, Caribbean coast of Panama, dredged at 200 m (CHL).

Etymology: The specific name is after Harry G. Lee who presented the unique shell from his collection.

Description: Shell small, solid, rounded, with a spire formed by 4 $\frac{3}{4}$ rapidly-expanding whorls. The protoconch has $\frac{3}{4}$ whorls, about 230 μ m in diameter and is apparently smooth, but under magnification 2 very fine spiral cordlets can be seen on its distal part. Teleoconch with 4 spiral whorls; ornamentation formed by spiral cords which are of similar size which do not produce an angulation; between them there are axial striae and microtubercles. Four spiral cords can be seen at the beginning of the 1st and 2nd whorls, 5 on the third and 4th and between 26 and 28 on the last; the cords which are near the suture and the umbilicus are finer and closer. Periphery uniformly rounded. Aperture rounded; outer lip reflected outwards, frontally widened and not crenulated. Columella arched, reflected, reducing it the umbilicus to a small fissure.

Dimensions: The holotype is 3.03 mm in height and 3.11 mm in diameter.

Habitat: Found on the continental slope. Collected with dredgings at 200 m.

Distribution: Only known from Isla Escudo de Veraguas, Caribbean coast of Panama, its type locality.

Remarks: *Haplocochlias harryleei* spec. nov. may be distinguished from the other known species because: the protoconch is apparently smooth, the periphery rounded, without keel or angulation, the umbilicus is almost closed, and the outer lip and the columella are reflected externally and widened frontally.

H. cubensis has a greater number of spiral cords and lacks axial striae between cords. *H. arrondoi* spec. nov. has an angled periphery.

moolenbeeki group

Remarks: The main differential characteristic of this group is the border of the outer lip being denticulate due to the projection of the spiral cords on its outer margin; the lip is not thickened nor reflected outwards. Another differential characteristic is the presence of a

depressed triangular area at the intersection of the outer lip, columella and periumbilical cord.

The name employed for this group is not that of the oldest described species but that of the most characteristic morphologically.

Haplocochlias moolenbeeki De Jong & Coomans, 1988 (Figure 24)

Haplocochlias swifti auct. non Vanatta, 1913.

Haplocochlias moolenbeeki de Jong & Coomans, 1988. *Studies on the Fauna of Curaçao and other Caribbean Islands* 69: 16, pl. 1, fig. 53 [Type locality: Aruba, harbour].

Figure 23. *Haplocochlias harryleei* spec. nov. A-C: holotype, diameter 3.11 mm, Isla Escudo de Veraguas, Caribbean coast of Panama (FLMNH); D, E: apex and protoconch of the holotype; F, G: microsculpture and detail of the last whorl.

Figura 23. *Haplocochlias harryleei* spec. nov. A-C: holotipo, diámetro 3,11 mm, Isla Escudo de Veraguas, costa caribeña de Panamá (FLMNH); D, E: ápice y protoconcha del holotipo; F, G: microescultura y detalle de la última vuelta.

Figure 24. *Haplocochlias moolenbeeki* de Jong & Coomans, 1988. A, B: paratype, 2.80 × 2.92 mm (MHNS ex coll. Verberne); C: protoconch; D: base of the columella, detail; E: microsculpture of the last whorl.

Figura 24. *Haplocochlias moolenbeeki* de Jong & Coomans, 1988. A, B: paratipo, 2,80 × 2,92 mm (MHNS ex col. Verberne); C: protoconcha; D: base de la columela, detalle; E: microescultura de la última vuelta.

Type material: The holotype of *Haplocochlias moolenbeeki* is deposited in ZMA (now Naturalis, Leiden; n° 2.87.050) (not examined); 17 paratypes in coll. F. Verberne deposited in ZMA (of which one now in MHNS donated by Robert Moolenbeek).

Other material examined: None.

Description: Original description of *H. moolenbeeki* in DE JONG & COOMANS (1988: 16): "The shell has 1 ½ nuclear and 4 postnuclear whorls. Aperture round, outer lip thickened, umbilicus present. The body whorl has 18 very fine spirals above the aperture, and two perceptibly more prominent spirals on the periphery (with one spiral in between); the penultimate whorl has 9 spirals".

The shell is turbiniform, strong and solid, with a spire formed by 4 ½ whorls that increase rapidly, separated by a marked suture. The protoconch has ¾ whorl, is totally smooth, lacks a labial varix and measures 215 µm in diameter. The teleoconch has 3 ¾ whorls and is ornamented by spiral cords and axial striae with micro tubercles in their interspaces. In apertural view we see 4 cords in the first whorls, 5 in the second and 32-34 in the last one; the cords are of regular size and distribution, without any peripheral carinae or a periumbilical larger cord; in the last half whorl the cords are more numerous and the interspaces between cords are reduced to a small groove. The axial striae in the first whorl are more separate and form rectangular hollows, later are more numerous and have closer interspaces. The surface of the hollows appears covered by micro tubercles.

Aperture rounded, prosocline. Parietal area covered by a very fine callous coat; columella arched, wider at the base, where 2 small protuberances can be seen. External lip sharp, the border crenulated by the presence of the spiral cords, not denticulate inside; on its base, near the columella a triangular depression can be seen. Umbilicus relatively wide, delimited by several spiral cords not very wide; inside 5-6 fine cordlets can be seen.

Dimensions: Holotype size: 4.4 in height, 4.7 mm in diameter. (H/D: 0,94)

The paratype studied measures 2.80 mm in height and 2.92 mm in diameter.

A specimen from Peanut Island, Palm Beach Co., Florida, USA is reported 5.5 mm (<www.jaxshells.org>, in Selected Western Atlantic Gastropods, edited by Harry Lee)

Habitat: Among rocks on east side Peanut Island, Palm Beach Co., Florida, USA (<www.jaxshells.org>).

Distribution: *H. moolenbeeki* has been recorded from Colombia (DÍAZ ET AL., 1990), Aruba and Curacao (DE JONG & COOMANS, 1988).

Remarks: The type of *H. moolenbeeki* could not be examined because the ZMA is in a period of restructuring and moving to Leiden. Only a paratype could be examined (Figs. 24A-B).

DE JONG & COOMANS (1988) remarked: "H. moolenbeeki was figured by ABBOTT (1974, fig. 457) as *H. swifti*, which species is not umbilicated and has less spirals, a thicker outer lip and carinae".

So, the only samples available for comparison are: that of DE JONG & COOMANS (1988: fig. 53, a drawing) and that of ABBOTT (1974, fig. 457). Actually, *H. moolenbeeki* differs from *H. swifti* mainly in lacking a thickening of the outer lip and because it is umbilicate, although its umbilicus is reduced to a small fissure.

The Cuban record of *H. moolenbeeki* by ESPINOSA ET AL. (1995) was later rejected by ESPINOSA, FERNÁNDEZ-GARCÉS & ROLÁN (2005) prior to the description of *H. nunezi* without explanation; also, there is no comparison between *H. nunezi* and *H. moolenbeeki* in that paper. The differences with *H. nunezi* are: *H. moolenbeeki* has a smooth protoconch; it lacks carinae which form an angle on the periphery of the shell; the spiral cords are regular in size and in distribution; its umbilicus is wider with 6 fine cordlets inside; it has two denticles on the base of the columella and a triangular depression on the base of the internal lip.

Haplocochlias nunezi Espinosa, Ortea & Fernández-Garcés, 2005 (Figures 25-27)

Haplocochlias sp. A. Redfern (2001), *Bahamian Seashells*: 15, figs. 66A-C.

Haplocochlias nunezi Espinosa, Ortea & Fernández-Garcés, 2005. *Avicennia* 17: 74, figs. 2A-C.
[Type locality: in front of the Instituto de Oceanología, La Habana, Cuba, 1.5 m].

Type material: The holotype of *Haplocochlias nunezi* is in IES, CITMA, Havana, Cuba.

Material examined: Cuba: 1 s, Havana, 1.5 m (MHNS). Nicaragua: 1 s, Witties, 15 m (MHNS). USA, Florida: 2 s, rocky reef, 45 m, Palm Beach (MCZ, 207094, in coll. McGinty as *H. swifti*); 1 s, Off Palm Beach, 54 m (MCZ 226853, in coll. McGinty as *H. swifti*); 1 s, 95 mi W Egmont Key, Hillsborough Co., dredged 76 m (CHL); 1 s, Fowey Rocks reef, Miami, Florida, under rubble, 3-3.6 m (CHL); 2 s, Off Palm Beach, Florida, 54 m (coll. McGinty, MCZ n° 226853 and 207094); 1 s, Monroe County, Molasses Reef, Upper Florida Keys, 7 m (FMNH 288191); 1 s, Monroe County, 24° 32' 47"N, 081° 24' 20"W, Looe Key back reef, Lower Florida Keys, 2.0 m (FMNH 288338); 1 s, Monroe County, 24° 32' 48"N, 081° 24' 48"W, Looe Key back reef, Lower Florida Keys, 6 m (FMNH 3008318); 1 s, Monroe County, off Halfmoon Shoal, 13 m (FMNH 328622); 1 s, Monroe County, Marquesas transect, in sand, 9 m (FMNH 328631); 1 s, Monroe County, 24° 27' 31"N, 082° 12' 22"W, Marquesas rock, 8 m (FMNH 330450); 1 s, Monroe County, The Horseshoe, off Marathon, 24° 39' 55"N, 080° 59' 34"W, 9 m (FMNH 330453); 1 s, Monroe County, Ramrod Key transect, W edge of Looe Key, 24° 33' 06"N, 081° 25' 56"W 10 m (FMNH 331907); 1 s, Monroe County, Dry Tortugas transect, 24° 32' 00"N, 082° 56' 29"W, 20.2 m (FMNH 333912). Bahamas: 67 s, Abaco Island, beach drift (CCR); 47 s, Abaco Island, 7 m, in coralline sediment (CCR); 1 sp, Abaco Island, live on the underside of a rock on the reef in 4.5 m (CCR); 1 s, Abaco Island, 35 m, in coralline sediment (CCR); 1 s, West End, Grand Bahama Island, beach (CHL); 1 s, N Current Cut, Eleuthera, beach (CHL); 1 s, South Riding Rocks, Cay Sal Bank, bottom sample 18 m (CHL); 1 s, Long Cay Mooring, Long Cay, bottom sample, 29 m (CHL). British Virgin Islands: 1 s, Deadman Chest, bottom sample, 18 m (CHL). Mexico: 1 s, Puerto Morelos, Yucatan, Mexico, 10-16 m (MHNS).

Description: Original description of *H. nunezi* in ESPINOSA *ET AL.* (2005).

To the original description we add: The shell of this species is large in comparison with the others of the genus (adult shells measure between 5.0 in height and 6.1 mm in diameter; H/D: 0.91); its spire is formed by 4.5-5 whorls. Ornamentation formed by spiral cords and axial striae, with microtubercles in the spaces between cords. The presence of 4 peripheral cords angulates the shell giving it a characteristic aspect; between them, there are other smaller spiral cords, whose number varies in relation to the degree of development of each individual. On the last whorl of the holotype there are 16 cordlets between the suture and the upper keel; 7 between the first and the second; 6 between the second and the third; 4 between the third and the fourth and approximately 20 between the fourth and the umbilicus.

Aperture rounded, peristome continuous, barely adherent. Outer lip sharp,

margin denticulate by the presence of cords and keels. Columella straight, is widened at the base, forming a triangular area in the intersection point between the outer lip, columella and periumbilical cord. Umbilicus narrow and deep, limited by a strong cord, 2-3 very fine cordlets can be observed within.

Dimensions: Maximum reported size: 6.3 mm high x 6.1 mm diameter (coll. McGinty, MCZ 226853 as *H. swifti*).

Habitat: Living specimens were collected in shallow water under rocks near the reef between 1.5 and 4.5 m in depth. Empty shells have been taken from sediment found between 5 and 53 m in depth.

Distribution: *H. nunezi* has been recorded in the Bahamas: Abaco (REDFERN, 2001 as *Haplocochlias* sp. A) and Grand Bahama Island (from material at ANSP); Cuba: North Havana Province (ESPINOSA *ET AL.*, 2005) USA: Florida Keys; Nicaragua: Witties; British Virgin Islands: Deadman Chest and

Figure 25. *Haplocochlias nunezi* Espinosa, Ortea & Fernández-Garcés, 2005. A: shell, diameter 5.43 mm, 95 miles W of Egmont Key, Hillsborough Co., Florida (CHL); B-F: shells, 5.39, 4.5, 4.5, 3.95, 2.8 mm, Abaco Island, Bahamas (CCR); G: shell, 2.8 mm, Havana, Cuba (MHNS).

Figura 25. *Haplocochlias nunezi* Espinosa, Ortea & Fernández-Garcés, 2005. A: concha, diámetro 5,43 mm, 95 millas al oeste de Egmont Key, Hillsborough Co., Florida (CHL); B-F: conchas, 5,39, 4,5, 4,5, 3,95, 2,8 mm, Abaco Island, Bahamas (CCR); G: concha, 2,8 mm, Habana, Cuba (MHNS).

Figure 26. *Haplocochlias nunezi* Espinosa, Ortea & Fernández-Garcés, 2005. A, B: shell, 6.3 × 6.1 mm, off Palm Beach, Florida, USA, 55 m (identified as *H. swiftii* in coll. McGinty, MCZ 226853); C: shell, diameter 5 mm, Palm Beach, Florida (as *H. swiftii* in coll. McGinty, MCZ 207094).

Figura 26. *Haplocochlias nunezi* Espinosa, Ortea & Fernández-Garcés, 2005. A, B: concha, 6,3 × 6,1 mm, frente a Palm Beach, Florida, EE.UU., 55 m (identificado como *H. swiftii* en col. McGinty, MCZ 226853); C: concha, diámetro 5 mm, Palm Beach, Florida (como *H. swiftii* en col. McGinty, MCZ 207094).

Mexico: Puerto Morelos, Yucatan, in the present work.

Remarks: The specimen of *H. nunezi* we examined (Fig. 19G) from Cuba, is less than 3 mm in diameter and so has not undergone the same degree of development as the holotype (5.7 mm in diameter); although we consider it as an adult individual it has not developed the same number of cords mentioned for the holo-

type. Otherwise it is identical with respect to all other characteristics.

In this particular specimen the columella is widened near the base, being reflected towards the umbilicus, giving the impression that it is straight and not arched; also the umbilicus is narrower than in all other adult shells examined.

The characters cited below are valid for the identification of juvenile individu-

Figure 27. *Haplocochlias nunezi* Espinosa, Ortea & Fernández-Garcés, 2005. A: apex, shell from Yucatan, Mexico (MHNS); B: protoconch, Nicaragua; C: protoconch, Florida; D-F: microsculpture of the last whorl.

Figura 27. *Haplocochlias nunezi* Espinosa, Ortea & Fernández-Garcés, 2005. A: ápide, concha de Yucatan, Mexico (MHNS); B: protoconcha, Nicaragua; C: protoconcha, Florida; D-F: microescultura de la última vuelta.

als as well as fully adult shells: (1) presence of 4 keels on the periphery of the last whorl, (2) umbilicus rather constricted, (3) columella straight and also the triangular space at the intersection of the outer lip with the columella and periumbilical cord, (4) outer lip crenulated.

The species was misidentified as *H. swifti* by ROSENBERG (1992: 42), who illustrated specimens from Grand Bahama Island (ANSP 370100) and whose Florida record is based on ANSP 181317 from Missouri Key and ANSP 313313 from off Palm Beach, being subsequently referred to *H. nunezi* by ROSENBERG *ET AL.* (2009). *Haplocochlias* sp. A of REDFERN (2001) was referred to *H. nunezi* by ESPINOSA *ET AL.* (2005).

Haplocochlias calidimaris (Pilsbry & McGinty, 1945) (Figure 28)

Paroiturbo calidimaris Pilsbry & McGinty, 1945. *Nautilus* 59: 56-57, pl. 6, fig. 4. [Type locality: 1 ½ miles off Cape Florida].

Type material: Holotype in ANSP (181319), paratypes in Weber and McGinty collections. Examined a photograph of the holotype sent by ANSP (Fig. 28A).

Material examined: USA, Florida: 3 s, Monroe County, Dry Tortugas transect Sta. D-21-FK-570, Florida Keys, 30 m (FMNH 333911).

Description: This is the original description in PILSBRY & MCGINTY (1945: 56-57): “*The moderately solid but not thick white shell is broadly turbinate, with a moderately elevated conic spire, rounded last whorl and rather narrow umbilicus, the last whorl encircled by ten major spiral cords. There are 3 ¾ strongly convex whorls, with a deep suture. The initial 1 ½ smooth, rounded whorls form the rather projecting nuclear shell. Following whorl matt, rounded (worn?), with traces of spiral cords at first, becoming well developed on its last half. Penult whorl has three strong spiral cords and a smaller one below the suture; the last whorl has about ten high, narrow spiral cords, those at and above the periphery are more widely spaced, with an interstitial spiral thread in the last half whorl. All of the intervals are crossed by low, fine axial threads. The umbilicus is small, its walls smooth within, and bounded by a high cord. The aperture is subcircular. Peristome thin, the outer margin scalloped,*

Haplocochlias nunezi is the most widely distributed species of the genus in the Caribbean, having been found from Florida to the Witties, Nicaragua. It is found in mainland as well as insular coastal waters. On some islands such as Abaco (Bahamas) populations must be very dense judging from the large number of shells found.

H. nunezi may be distinguished from *H. moolenbeeki* by the larger size of its protoconch and by having cords on its surface; by having 4 cords which look as carinae and form angles at the periphery of the shell; by having the columella almost straight and reflected towards the umbilicus, which in adult shells is reduced to a narrow fissure.

columella narrow, nearly straight. Parietal callus rather thin”.

Diameter 2 mm, height 1.75 mm.

The protoconch has ¾ of whorl, measuring about 260 µm, and it has 3 spiral cords on its surface and a thick labial varix.

The teleoconch has 2 ½ whorls and is covered entirely by spiral cords, axial grooves and microtubercles in the interspace between cords. In apertural position the shell shows 3 cords in the first whorl and 9-10 on the last whorl. The cords are very prominent, narrower than the interspaces, which are concave and are covered by axial striae very regular in size and disposition.

Inside the umbilicus 2-3 spiral cordlets can be seen; also fine axial grooves, more numerous and dense than those located in the spaces between cords.

The outer lip is crenulated so as to form a scalloped margin, not thickened or with denticles on its inner side, modi-

Figure 28. *Haplocochlias calidimaris* (Pilsbry & McGinty, 1945). A: holotype, diameter 2.0 mm (ANSP 181319); B, C: shell, apical and apertural view, diameter 1.8 mm (FMNH 333911); D: protoconch, same shell; E: apex and microsculpture.

Figura 28. *Haplocochlias calidimaris* (Pilsbry & McGinty, 1945). A: holotype, diámetro 2,0 mm (ANSP 181319); B, C: concha, vista apical y apertural, diámetro 1,8 mm (FMNH 333911); D: protoconcha de la misma concha; E: ápice y microescultura.

fied by many spiral cords that determine its outline.

A shell studied measures 1.62 mm in height and 1.81 mm in diameter (H/D: 0.9).

Habitat: This is probably a subtidal species, living under stones, in 70 ft (21 m). North Inlet of Lake Worth, Palm Beach and Ft. Myers Beach, Florida (PILSBRY & MCGINTY, 1945). At 20 m deep (ABBOTT, 1974).

Bathymetric range: 0 to 21 m

Distribution: USA: Florida: East Florida, West Florida (PILSBRY & MCGINTY, 1945); South half of Florida (ABBOTT, 1974); Moín, Costa Rica (ROBINSON & MONTOYA 1987). Range: 26.8°N to 10.01°N; 83.08°W to 80°W.

Remarks: PILSBRY & MCGINTY (1945: 57) indicated: "This species has more spiral cords than *C. [error for Parviturbo] weberi* and lacks the imperfect axial folds which make the upper and the lowest cords nodulose in that species. It is similar in figure to *P. francesae* [now *Haplocochlias francesae*], but is much smaller, and the last half whorl has a spiral thread in the intervals (not showing in the face view). It differs from *P. zacalles* by the same character, and also by the form of the umbilicus and the columella. Possibly none of the specimens are fully adult, as the lip is still thin, not thickened as in similar species; but the sculptural characters show that it is not the immature stage of any other known species.

The epipodial cirri have been observed in specimens from the North Inlet of Lake Worth".

Since its original description, *Parviturbo calidimaris* has not been recorded in any malacological work, except by ABBOTT (1974); this work being a compilation of the American species of known mollusks only mentions the area where the type material was found, Florida. ROBINSON & MONTOYA (1987) recorded this species from Moín, Costa Rica, but this mention requires confirmation, because on the basis of the material studied, we believe that the area of distribution of *P. calidimaris* is confined to the Floridan coast.

The larger number of spiral cordlets, the absence of axial lamellae in the interspaces and of nodose cordlets, among other characters, prompted us to transfer this species to the genus *Haplocochlias*.

In our opinion, the species with which *Haplocochlias calidimaris* has most similarity is *H. francesae*, species with which it shares, in addition to certain morphological characters, the bathymetric range and habitat. *Haplocochlias calidimaris* differs from *H. francesae* by having the protoconch ornamented with spiral cordlets, because it has the edge of the outer lip modified by the presence of spiral cords and the cordlets in their interspace (18-20 can be observed on the edge of the outer lip), and also in having the umbilicus wider and with 2-3 fine spiral cordlets and axial striae that are very dense inside.

Haplocochlias pacorubioi spec. nov. (Figures 29, 30)

Type material: Holotype (15.05/60044, Figs. 29A-B) and 1 paratype deposited in MNCN (15.05/60045). Others paratypes in the following: MNHN (IM-2012-2522, 1 s, Fig. 29C), MCZ (377779, 1 s, Fig. 29D), MHNS (100575, 1 s), IES (1 s), all from type locality.

Other material examined: Cuba: 1 s, Cayo Matias, Archipelago of Canarreos, 18 m (MHNS); 1 s, Guajimico, 2 m (MHNS); 4 s, Cienfuegos, 35 m (MHNS); 1 s, Rancho Luna Beach, 40 m (MHNS); 1 s, Rancho Luna Beach, 45 m (MHNS).

Type locality: Rancho Luna Beach, Cienfuegos, Cuba, at 35 m.

Etymology: The species name is dedicated to Francisco (Paco) Rubio, brother of the first author recently passed away.

Description: Shell of small size, robust, almost as wide as high, turbiniform, spire comprised of 4 ½ whorls separated by a deep suture. Protoconch to-

tally smooth without spiral cordlets, measuring about 210 μm, and ¾ whorl. Teleoconch 3 ¾ whorls. Ornamentation formed by spiral cords of varying cali-

Figure 29. *Haplocochlias pacorubioi* spec. nov. A: holotype, 2.81 mm height \times 2.5 mm diameter (MNCN); B: paratype, 3.0 mm (MNCN); C: paratype, 2.6 mm height (MNHN); D: paratype, height 2.3 mm (MCZ), all from Rancho Luna Beach, Cienfuegos, Cuba; E, F: apex and protoconch.

Figura 29. *Haplocochlias pacorubioi* spec. nov. A: holotipo, 2.81 mm altura \times 2.5 mm diámetro (MNCN); B: paratipo, 3.0 mm (MNCN); C: paratipo, altura 2.6 mm (MNHN); D: paratipo, altura 2.3 mm (MCZ), todos de Playa Rancho Luna, Cienfuegos, Cuba; E, F: ápice y protoconcha.

Figure 30. *Haplocochlias pacorubioi* spec. nov. A: protoconch; B, C: microsculpture and detail of last whorl.

Figura 30. *Haplocochlias pacorubioi* spec. nov. A: protoconcha; B, C: microescultura y detalle de la última vuelta.

bre, and by axial striae and microtubercles in the interspaces between cords. On the first whorl the striae are crossed by the cords forming cells of regular size; after the second whorl the striae are fused and become arched resembling small spirally aligned fish scales. The spiral cords are distributed thus: 4 on the first whorl; 6 on the second, of which the fourth is peripheral and more prominent; 12 on the third whorl, of which 5, 9 and 11 are more prominent producing an angulation of the periphery; on the last whorl the number of cords is between 40 and 46, of varying size.

Aperture rounded, almost circular, peristome barely adherent. Columella thickened, not reflected; on the inner lip there is a wide and concave area at the intersection with the umbilical cords; outer lip with sharp border and denticulate, its inner aspect with crenulations corresponding to the outer end of the spiral cords.

Umbilicus reduced to a narrow fissure, within which some cords are visible.

Dimensions: The holotype measures 2.81 mm in height and 2.50 mm in diameter. The largest paratype is 3.4 mm in diameter.

Habitat: The shells were collected in sediment from a coralline bottom at between 18 and 35 m.

Distribution: Only known from the south coast of Cuba at Cayo Matías (archipelago of Los Canarreos) and Rancho Luna Beach, Cienfuegos.

Remarks: *Haplocochlias pacorubioi* spec. nov. may be distinguished from the other species of the genus by the completely smooth protoconch, the presence of three strong peripheral cords forming keels which make the shell angulate, the axial striae in the shape of scales, the outer lip with a denticulate border and inner crenulation, and the umbilicus, which is reduced to a narrow fissure.

Another character that distinguishes the species from its congeners is the pentagonal cells on the first whorl of the teleoconch which disappear where the axial striae are joined together.

H. moolenbeeki differs by its larger size, having a larger protoconch with cords, and a greater number of spiral cords on the last whorl.

H. panamensis has fewer spiral cords, a smaller protoconch diameter, and numerous elongate and less prominent denticles.

Haplocochlias erici (Strong & Hertlein, 1939) (Figure 31)

Liotia erici Strong & Hertlein, 1939. *Allan Hancock Pacific Expeditions*, 2: 237, pl. 21 fig. 9. [Type locality: Bahía Honda, Isla Cohiba, Provincia de Vergara, Pacific coast of Panama].

Parviturbo erici (Strong & Hertlein, 1939): Keen (1971) *Sea shells of Tropical West America*: 345, fig. 123.

Type material: Holotype in California Academy of Sciences Paleont. (729). Not examined.

Material examined: Mexico, Pacific coast: 4 s, Puertecitos, Baja California (Gulf side), 1-3 m (LACM 64-31). Costa Rica, Pacific coast: 8 s, 1 mile offshore between Bahía Elena and Juanillo Bay, Guanacaste Province, 25-52 m (LACM 72-12); 4 s, 1 mile off beach, Bahía Brasilito, Guanacaste Province, 18 m (LACM 72-40); 13 s, anchorage inside small islet 1.5 km S of Punta Quepos, Puntarenas Province, 21 m, sandy bottom (LACM 72-57); 7 s, small islets off Quepos, Puntarenas Province, 22 m, gravel and cobble (LACM 72-59).

Description: The original description in STRONG & HERTLEIN (1939) is as follows: "Shell small, turbinate, solid, grayish white; nuclear whorls 1 ½, smooth, very small; postnuclear whorls 3 ½ well rounded, sutures slightly channeled; spiral

sculpture of 4 raised threads on the first postnuclear whorl and 8 on the second; on the last whorl there are about 16 fine threads above the shoulder, followed by 12 slightly larger threads on the periphery and upper part of the base, umbilicus bordered by 2

Figure 31. *Haplocochlias erici* (Strong & Hertlein, 1939). A, B: shells, diameter 2.45 mm and 1.7 mm (LACM 72-12 and LACM 72-59); C: protoconch, same shell as B; D, E: detail of the microsculpture, same shell as A.

Figura 31. *Haplocochlias erici* (Strong & Hertlein, 1939). A, B: conchas, diámetro 2,45 mm y 1,7 mm (LACM 72-12 and LACM 72-59); C: protoconcha, misma concha que B; D, E: detalles de la microescultura, misma concha que A.

still larger cords with fine intercalary threads; axial sculpture of fine, close-spaced riblets in the interspaces between the spiral threads over the entire surface; periphery of last whorl and base well rounded, umbilicus narrow, with a deep groove between the inner lip and the last spiral cord; aperture circular, the posterior angle falling low on the body whorl; outer lip thick, smooth; inner lip thin where it borders the umbilicus, spreading above. Operculum unknown".

Shell of small size, robust, turbiniform, spire formed by 4 whorls of rapid growth, separated by a deep suture. The protoconch is $\frac{3}{4}$ of whorl, smooth and measures 170 μm . The teleoconch has $\frac{3}{4}$ whorls, in apertural view are observed in the 1st and 2nd whorls 4 spiral cords and 16 on the last one. In the first whorl, the spiral cords stretch in zig-zag and cross with axial striae forming hexagonal cells. Ornamentation formed by prominent spiral cords, narrower than their interspaces; axial striae which are transformed into lamellae that occupy the spaces between cords, also with micro tubercles.

Aperture rounded, peristome continuous; columella thick, not reflected, widened at its base where is observed a triangular depression at the junction

with outer lip and the umbilical cord; outer lip thick, margin crenulated and contour slightly angled by the presence of spiral cords. Umbilicus variable depending on the H/D parameter of each shell.

Dimensions: The type measures: diameter, 2.0 mm; height, 1.3 mm.

The photographed specimens measure: 2.28 mm in height and 2.45 mm in diameter (H/D: 0.93); 1.95 mm in height and 1.75 mm in diameter (H/D: 1.11).

Habitat: From 5 to 16 m (STRONG & HERTLEIN, 1939); 10 to 50 m (KEEN, 1971).

Distribution: Bahía Honda, Pacific coast of Panama (STRONG & HERTLEIN, 1939); Guaymas, Mexico to Gorgona Island, Pacific coast of Colombia (KEEN, 1971).

Remarks: In size and shape this species is very similar to the last ones, but the lack of prominent spiral sculpture makes it entirely different from any other species described from the Pacific coast.

The shells with H/D: 0.93 present a much more open umbilicus with 4 cordlets inside, besides growth lines. Shells with H/D: 1.11 present a narrower umbilicus and the inner cordlets are scarcely visible.

Haplocochlias conceptionensis (Lowe, 1935) (Figure 32)

? *Homalopoma conceptionensis* Lowe, 1935. *Transactions of the San Diego Society of Natural History*, 8 (6): 24, pl. 4 fig.3. [Type locality: Concepción Bay, Baja California, Mexico].

Parviturbo conceptionensis (Lowe, 1935): Keen, 1971. *Sea Shells of Tropical West America*: 345, fig. 122.

Type material: Holotype in Lowe collection in SDSNH (11593).

Material examined: Mexico: 2 s, E of Isla Willard, Bahía San Luis Gonzaga, Baja California, 18-27 m, sand bottom (LACM 69-25); 14 s, 1 mile off Olas Altas, Mazatlan, Sinaloa, 18 m; 7 s, Bahía San Carlos, Guaymas, Sonora, 31.1 m (LACM 178541); Panama, Pacific coast: 2 s, Venado Island, Canal Zone, intertidal (LACM 70-15); 7 s, Palo Seco, Canal Zone, intertidal, upper and middle zones (LACM 72-74).

Description: Original description in LOWE (1935): "Shell small, pure white, solid, globose, suture strongly appressed; five whorls, including the smooth nucleus, strongly tabulated by a peripheral keel. On the penultimate whorl is a strong sutural

keel and two almost equally strong just below it; on the flat shoulder just anterior to the major keel are three secondary flat spiral cords with wide interspaces. On the body whorl, just below the suture, are two major spiral cords with a secondary spiral thread

Figure 32. *Haplocochlias conceptionensis* (Lowe, 1935). A, B: shells, 4.6 and 3.1 mm, San Carlos Bay, Guaymas, Sonora, Mexico (LACM 178541); C: protoconch of Fig. B; E, F: sculpture and detail, same shell as A.

Figura 32. *Haplocochlias conceptionensis* (Lowe, 1935). A, B: conchas, 4,6 y 3,1 mm, Bahía San Carlos, Guaymas, Sonora, México (LACM 178541); C: protoconcha, misma concha que B; E, F: microescultura y detalle, misma concha que A.

between; next three of the strong cords with four spiral threads anterior to each; posterior to the last are thirteen flattened spiral cords of about equal strength and equal interspaces. The entire surface between the spiral sculpture is covered with microscopic, diagonally radial striae. Aperture circular, outer lip thin; heavy callus on the columella, back of which is a large, flattened chink with four radial threads on its flat surface. Diameter 5.6 mm, altitude 5.6 mm".

Shell large, almost as high as wide (HD: 0.90), turbiniform, robust, spire formed by slightly more than 5 whorls increasing rapidly, separated by a deep suture. The protoconch has $\frac{3}{4}$ of whorl, completely smooth and measuring 180 μ m in diameter. The teleoconch has $4\frac{1}{4}$ to $4\frac{1}{2}$ whorls. Typical ornamentation formed by spiral cords, axial striae and micro tubercles. In apertural view 4 spiral cords are observed in the first whorl, 5 in the second, 6 in the third and 17 at the last one, of which the two upper ones, subsutural, are smaller in size; from the 3rd to 6th, peripheral cords are more prominent, spaced and angle the shell; the remaining, basal, are rounded, regular in size, as wide as their interspaces.

Aperture oval, prosocline; parietal area with a thin callous layer; columella arched, widened towards the base in which a little deep depression is observed; outer lip not very thick, reflected, edge sharpening and finely crenulated. Umbilicus narrow, deep, delimited by a not very thick spiral cord, inside a spiral cordlet is observed.

Habitat: Collected from the intertidal to 28 m.

Distribution: Head of the Gulf of California to Panama (KEEN, 1971; ABBOTT, 1974).

Remarks: Described by LOWE (1935) in the genus *Homalopoma*, but expressing some doubts about its generic placement: "As there was no sign of an operculum attached to the animal, I am in doubt whether to place the species in *Homalopoma* or *Liotia*".

KEEN (1971) places *Homalopoma conceptionensis* Lowe, 1935 in *Parviturbo*, along with other species described previously in *Liotia*. However, in our opinion, *H. conceptionensis* has all those characters described for *Haplocochlias*, and no those of *Parviturbo* mentioned in the introduction; so we decided to place the species in this genus.

Haplocochlias francesae (Pilsbry & McGinty, 1945) (Figure 33)

Parviturbo francesae Pilsbry & McGinty, 1945. *The Nautilus*, 59: 56, pl. 6, fig. 6. [Type locality: Off Palm Beach, Florida, USA].

Type material: Holotype in ANSP (181316) examined on photograph; paratypes in McGinty collection at MCZ (226843 and 207086), examined.

Material examined: USA, Florida: 1 s, Off Palm Beach, paratype, McGinty collection (MZC 226843); 1 s, Palm Beach, paratype, McGinty collection (MZC 207086); 1 s, SW Florida (26° 52.36' N – 83° 27.22' W), dredged in 54 m (CEG); 2 s, off Sombrero Light, Kay Vaca, Monroe Co., dredged 60 m (CHL); 4 s, off Cedar Kays, Levy Co., dredged 54 m (CHL); 24 s, Monroe County, Key Colony Beach transect, 24° 39' 04"N, 080° 59' 16"W, 36 m (FMNH 328629); 3 s, Monroe County, Dry Tortugas transect, 24° 28' 52"N, 082° 56' 59"W, 34 m (FMNH 328629); 3 s, Monroe County, off Looe Key, 24° 31' 20"N, 081° 25' 55"W, 53-54 m (FMNH 328725); 1 s, Monroe County, Infaunal Mollusk Survey, Marquesas transect, 24° 23' 33"N, 082° 27' 59"W, 49 m (FMNH 333876); 4 s, Monroe County, Windley Key transect, 24° 53' 35"N, 080° 31' 47"W, 39 m (FMNH 333874); 1 s, Monroe County, Ramrod Key transect, 24° 35' 20"N, 081° 25' 56"W, 7 m (FMNH 333873); 6 s, Monroe County, Ramrod Key transect, 24° 31' 35"N, 081° 25' 56"W, 43 m (FMNH 333774); 1 s, Monroe County, SW corner of Looe Key National Marine Sanctuary, 24° 31' 56"N, 081° 25' 55"W, 36 m (FMNH 332030); 1 s, Monroe County, Ramrod Key transect, off Looe Key, 24° 32' 14"N, 081° 25' 56"W, 33-36 m (FMNH 333873); 1 s, Monroe County, Sand Key transect, 24° 25' 56"N, 081° 53' 19"W, 53 m (FMNH 333873); 15 s, Monroe County, Carysfort Reef transect, 25° 13' 23"N, 080° 11' 24"W, 53 m (FMNH 328625); 1 s, Monroe County, Key Colony Beach transect, 24° 38' 22"N, 080° 59' 01"W, 57 m (FMNH 333905);

Figure 33. *Haplocochlias francesae* (Pilsbry & McGinty, 1945). A: holotype, height 3.15 mm (ANSP 181316); B-D: shell, 3.06 mm, SW Florida (26° 52.36' N – 83° 27.22' W) (CEG); E: protoconch, same shell as D; F: microsculpture of the last whorl.

Figura 33. *Haplocochlias francesae* (Pilsbry & McGinty, 1945). A: *holotipo*, altura 3,15 mm (ANSP 181316); B-D: *concha*, 3,06 mm, SO Florida (26° 52,36' N – 83° 27,22' W) (CEG); E: *protoconcha*, misma *concha* que D; F: *microescultura* de la última *vuelta*.

1 s, Monroe County, Ramrod Key transect, 24° 31' 56"N, 081° 25' 55"W, 35 m (FMNH 333913); 1 s, Monroe County, off Halfmoon Shoal, 24° 35' 20"N, 081° 25' 56"W, 50 m (FMNH 328621); 1 s, Monroe County, Key Colony Beach transect, 24° 38' 00"N, 080° 58' 54"W, 69 m (FMNH 333906); 2 s, Monroe County, off Halfmoon Shoal transect, 24° 23' 16"N, 082° 28' 08"W, 49-50 m (FMNH 333873); 5 s, Monroe County, Carysfort Reef transect, 25° 12' 55"N, 080° 10' 38"W, 79 m (FMNH 333873); 3 s, Key Colony Beach transect, 24° 42' 14"N, 081° 00' 14"W, 72 m (FMNH 328626).

Description: The original description in PILSBRY & MCGINTY (1945: 56) is as follows: "The moderately solid but not thick white shell is broadly turbinate, with somewhat elevated but short spire, rounded periphery and narrow umbilicus, and with sculpture of strong spiral cords, nine on the last whorl. There are 4 ½ strongly convex whorls, with deep suture. The first whorl is smooth; the next (or first post nuclear whorl) has 3 or 4 spiral cords crossed by delicate axial threads. The last whorl has nine strong spiral cords, the upper one somewhat smaller, the lower or ninth cord bordering the umbilicus. The cords are separated by decidedly wider intervals, which are closely sculptured across by delicate axial threads. The umbilicus is narrow and deep, its walls smooth within. The aperture is subcircular, peristome somewhat thickened within, continuous, with scalloped outer margin. Diameter 3.4 mm, height: 3.15 mm."

Protoconch smooth of just ¾ of whorl and about 290 µm in diameter. Spaces between the cords with axial threads, more distant in the first two whorls of the teleoconch forming quadrangular cells and much more tight and numerous in last whorl and a half as lamellae. Spaces between axial threads are covered by microtubercles. At the base of the columella, the point of contact with the periumbilical cord forms a slightly depressed area.

Dimensions: The shell examined measures 2.93 mm in height and 3.06 mm diameter (H/D: 0.96).

Habitat: A circalittoral species, its bathymetric range is between 54 and 91 m deep.

Distribution: Limited to East and West Florida, USA. Recorded from off Palm Beach (PILSBRY & MCGINTY, 1945); southwest of Johns Pass, West Florida (ABBOTT, 1974).

Remarks: The scalloped outer lip, the number of spiral cords and the axial striae forming fine lamellae characterize this species and distinguish it from its congeners.

PILSBRY & MCGINTY (1945) comment: "This is a broader shell than *C. [error for Parviturbo] weberi* with narrower umbilicus, and having exceptionally delicate and beautiful sculpture in the intervals of the spiral cords. The projecting embryonic shell of only one whorl, or at most one and one-fourth, is also characteristic".

Haplocochlias francesae is a species that in the adult stage cannot be mistaken in its determination. However, immature stages can be confused with *H. calidimaris* and vice versa. *Haplocochlias francesae*, contrary to *H. calidimaris*, has a smooth protoconch; the number of spiral cords remains unchanged, not being doubled in the latest half whorl; but above all, its axial striation, enhanced by the number and proximity of fine lamellae is one of the morphological characters which most helps for their differentiation.

Haplocochlias panamensis spec. nov. (Figure 34)

Type material: Holotype in MNCN (15.05/60046).

Type locality: Coiba Island, Pacific coast of Panama.

Etymology: The specific name indicates the country where the species was collected.

Description: Shell small, almost as high as wide, very solid, of turbiniform aspect, spire formed by five rapidly expanding whorls separated by a deep suture. Protoconch ¾ whorl, apparently smooth and measuring about 230 µm in maximum diameter. Teleoconch formed by 4 ¼ whorls; the ornamentation is formed by spiral cords and axial striae with microtubercles in the interspaces

between cords. On the first whorl 4-5 spiral cords can be seen; on the last there are 28-29 strong spiral cords, three of which (the 5th, close to the suture, and the 9th and 12th, peripheral) form angles at the periphery of the shell. The spaces between cords are slightly concave, within there are very numerous axial lamellae, after the first teleoconch whorl they become very numer-

Figure 34. *Haplocochlias panamensis* spec. nov. A, B: holotype, diameter 4.18 mm (MNCN); C: detail of the umbilicus; D: protoconch of the holotype; E: microsculpture and detail of the last whorl.

Figura 34. *Haplocochlias panamensis* spec. nov. A, B: holotipo, diámetro 4,18 mm (MNCN); C: detalle del ombbligo; D: protoconcha del holotipo; E: microescultura y detalle de la última vuelta.

ous and more crowded; the spaces between them are occupied by microtubercles. Aperture ovoid, prosocline; peristome continuous. Outer lip very thick, slightly modified by the presence of spiral cords, on the inner aspect are numerous elongate denticles that become wider as they proceed to the columella. Parietal area covered by a thin callous coat. Columella very arched, widened basally, showing 3-4 small denticles and a quadrangular space at the convergence of the umbilical cord, the columella and the outer lip. Umbilicus partially occluded by the basal enlargement of the columella and the presence of several strong cords; under high magnification 2-3 fine spiral threads can be seen within.

Haplocochlias sp. (Figure 35)

Material examined: 1 s, Caribbean coast of Panama (CFR).

Description: Shell of small size, strong, compact, turbiniform, spire formed by 5 rapidly expanding whorls, tricarinate, separated by a marked suture. The protoconch is apparently smooth, has $\frac{3}{4}$ whorl and measures 230 μ m. The teleoconch has 4 $\frac{1}{4}$ whorls which are totally covered by spiral cords, their interspaces covered by axial grooves and microtubercles. Spiral cords are distributed thus: 4-5 on the first whorl, 5 on the second, 8-9 on the third and 35 on the last. The cords are of regular size, except the 8th, the 14th and the 17th, which are more prominent and angle the periphery of the shell, giving a tricarinate aspect. After the first teleoconch whorl the axial striae become more numerous and crowded. Aperture ovoid; outer lip thick, externally finely crenulated, inside within having thin and elongated spiral denticles. The columella is shorter than its congener from Coiba Island and it has no clearly triangular area characteristic of the group, although an angulation is formed at the convergence of the outer lip, columella and periumbilical cord. Umbilicus par-

Dimensions: the holotype measures 3.78 mm in height and 4.18 mm in diameter (H/D: 0.90).

Habitat: Species collected in dredgings at 200 m in depth on the continental slope.

Distribution: Only known from Coiba Island, Pacific coast of Panama.

Remarks: *Haplocochlias* spec. nov. differs from the remaining species of the group, by its three keels which angulate the periphery; by the denticulation of the lip and most notably, the denticulation of the columella, a condition not observed in any other species of the genus.

The most similar species is *Haplocochlias pacorubioi* spec. nov., but it lacks the quadrangular depression and the denticulation in the columella.

tially occluded, deep, with 1-2 spiral cordlets visible within.

Dimensions: 3.9 mm in height and 4.2 in diameter (H/D: 0.89).

Habitat: Unknown. Probably in shallow water.

Distribution: Only known from Caribbean coast of Panama.

Remarks: *Haplocochlias* sp. 1 is very similar to *H. panamensis*, with three very thick cords that form angles on the periphery of the shell, however, the distribution of the cords on the teleoconch is more regular. *H. panamense* has more irregular cords on the teleoconch, fewer spiral cords and a narrower umbilicus.

An important fact is that the specimens of *H. panamensis* and *Haplocochlias* sp. studied here originated on opposite sides of the Panama isthmus; *H. panamensis* comes from Coiba Island, Pacific coast of Panama, and *Haplocochlias* sp. from the Caribbean coast of Panama. Despite the conchological similarities between these two taxa, they are treated as distinct based in part on zoogeography.

Figure 35. *Haplocochlias* sp. A, B: shell, diameter 4.20 mm (CFR); C: protoconch of the same shell; D: microsculpture of the last whorl.

Figura 35. Haplocochlias sp. A, B: concha, diámetro 4,20 mm (CFR); C: protoconcha de la misma concha; D: microescultura de la última vuelta.

Haplocochlias turbinus (Dall, 1889) (Figure 36)

Cyclostrema turbinum Dall, 1889. *Bulletin of the Museum of Comparative Zoology* 18: 393-394, pl. 33, fig. 6 [not 5 as erroneously referred in the text]. [Type locality: Off Havana, Cuba, 80 fathoms (146 m)].
Parviturbo turbinum (Dall, 1889): Pilsbry & McGinty, 1945.

Type material: Holotype in USNM (214278). Examined by SEM.

Other material examined: None.

Description: Original description in DALL (1889): "Shell small, thin, subconic, with four rounded whorls and a minute glassy nucleus; radiating sculpture of fine oblique incremental lines, which on the early whorls rise into very fine threads, visible crossing the interspaces of the spiral sculpture; spiral sculpture of (on the last whorl) about seven strong smooth even cinguli on the top of the whorl, and fourteen or fifteen more rather smaller from the periphery to the brink of the umbilicus; there are also a few finer ones, especially three near the suture, and occasionally some spiral striation faintly indicated; on the top of the whorl the interspaces are about twice as wide as the threads, but not so wide on the base. The whorls, periphery, and base are evenly rounded, the suture distinct, not channelled; the umbilicus perforate, with smoothish walls; aperture half as high as the shell, oblique, nearly circular, with sharp, simple, slightly expanded edges. Max. diam. 3.25; alt. 2.75 mm."

Dimensions: The holotype, on the photograph received from the USNM with scale, is 3.0 x 3.0 mm).

The shell has a turbiniform shape, it is somewhat robust and its spire is formed by 4 whorls, of which $\frac{3}{4}$ correspond to the protoconch and $3\frac{1}{4}$ to the teleoconch; its periphery is rounded and on it neither a keel nor thickened cords can be seen. The protoconch measures 240 μ m, and, due to its deteriorated state we have not observed if it is smooth or has spiral cordlets. The teleoconch is decorated with spiral cords and axial striae in their interspaces. There are 3-4 spiral cords on the first whorl, 4 on

the second, and 24 on the last one; the cords are usually narrower than their interspaces. Aperture rounded; outer lip thickened, apparently not crenulated on its external border or denticulate within; columella thick, slightly arched and reflected towards the umbilicus without occluding it. At the confluence of the outer lip, columella and periumbilical cord, a triangular area is formed which characterizes the species. Just before the outer lip of the last whorl a thickening is present (as seen in some other species of *Haplocochlias*). Umbilicus narrow and deep, 2 cordlets are visible within.

Habitat: Species collected by dredging in deep circalittoral waters and on the continental slope. DALL (1889) records it at 146 m (80 fathoms) in depth.

Distribution: USA: North Carolina (DALL, 1889; PORTER, 1974); Cuba: North Havana Province (PILSBRY & MCGINTY, 1945). Range: 34.2°N to 23°N; 82°W to 76.5°W.

Remarks: Originally described by DALL (1889) in the genus *Cyclostrema*, later transferred to *Parviturbo* by PILSBRY & MCGINTY (1945), indicating only: "apparently belongs here". In our opinion, *Cyclostrema turbinum* belongs to the genus *Haplocochlias*, if we take into account the general shape of the shell, the ornamentation consisting of many spiral cords and axial striae covering their interspaces and especially the triangular area formed at the convergence of the outer lip, columella, and periumbilical cord.

ungrouped

The species that follow are not grouped with any of the preceding taxa because each has characters which

differ sufficiently from one another as well as from the preceding grouped species.

Figure 36. *Haplocochlias turbinus* (Dall, 1889). A, B: holotype, diameter 3.0 mm (USNM - 214278); C: apical view.

Figura 36. *Haplocochlias turbinus* (Dall, 1889). A, B: holotipo, diámetro 3,0 mm (USNM - 214278); C: vista apical.

***Haplocochlias pauciliratus* spec. nov.** Rubio, Rolán & Lee (Figures 37, 38)

Type material: Holotype in FLMNH (457009) (Fig. 37A). Paratypes in MNCN (1 s, 15.05/60042), MHNS (1 s, 100573), MCZ (1 s) and CHL (1 s) from Gibbons Bay, Hamilton, Bermuda.

Other material examined: Bermuda: 16 s, from Gibbons Bay, Hamilton, Bermuda, shore drift (CHL). **Type locality:** Mt. Olympus Reef, 12 miles NNW of West End, Grand Bahama Island, Bahamas.

Etymology: The specific name alludes to the scarcity of spiral cords.

Description: Shell very small, almost as high as wide, solid, turbiniform, spire formed by 3 rapidly-expanding whorls, separated by a wide and deep suture, which on the last whorl is further widened and separates from the preceding whorl. The protoconch has $\frac{3}{4}$ whorl, totally smooth and 250 μ m in maximum diameter. Teleoconch formed by $2\frac{1}{4}$ - $2\frac{3}{4}$ whorls; ornamentation typical,

formed by spiral cords, axial striae, and microtubercles in the spaces between cords. On the last whorl 11-12 spiral cords can be seen, usually wide and prominent, except a few which are finer and intercalated in the subsutural and dorsal areas. Aperture rounded, prosocline; peristome continuous. outer lip modified by the presence of spiral cords, not widened or crenulated within; col-

Figure 37. *Haplocochlias pauciliratus* spec. nov. A, B: holotype, 1.5 mm, Mt. Olympus Reef, 12 miles NNW of West End, Bahamas (FLMNH, ex CHL). C-F: paratypes, all from Gibbons Bay, Bermuda; C: 1.3 mm (MNCN); D: 1.36 mm (MHNS); E, F: 1.2 mm (the same shell) (CHL).

Figura 37. *Haplocochlias pauciliratus* spec. nov. A, B: holotipo, 1,5 mm, Mt. Olympus Reef, 12 millas NNO de West End, Bahamas (FMNH, ex CHL). C-F: paratipos de Gibbons Bay, Bermuda; C: 1,3 mm (MNCN); D: 1,36 mm (MHNS); E, F: 1,2 mm (la misma concha) (CHL).

Figure 38. *Haplocochlias pauciliratus* spec. nov. A: protoconch of the holotype. B: protoconch of the paratype of Fig. 37D, Bermuda; C: microsculpture of the last whorl of the holotype; D: microsculpture of the last whorl of the paratype of Figure 37C, from Bermuda.

Figura 38. Haplocochlias pauciliratus spec. nov. A: protoconcha del paratipo de la Fig. 37D, Bermudas; C: microescultura de la última vuelta del holotipo; D: microescultura de la última vuelta del paratipo de la Figura 37C, Bermudas.

umella arched, reflected externally. Umbilicus relatively wide and deep, delimited by a strong cord, two fine spiral cordlets and feeble growth lines within.

Dimensions: The holotype measures 1.47 mm in height and 1.5 mm in diameter.

Habitat: An infralittoral species which in the Bahamas was found on

sandy bottom with fragments of coralline algae.

Distribution: Only known from NNW West End, Grand Bahama and Gibbons Bay, Bermuda.

Remarks: *Haplocochlias pauciliratus* spec. nov. differs from the other species in the genus, particularly from those with a smooth protoconch by the reduced number of spiral cords, their thickness and regularity, as well as the H/D ratio very close to 1.

We have only been able to examine one shell (the holotype) from Bahamas, and its morphological characters are almost identical to the shells from Bermuda. Only slight differences in their morphology can be observed and we believe these fall within normal intraspecific variability.

An unusual feature in the ornamentation of this species is that the axial

striae maintain a certain regularity in their separation throughout the teleoconch. Only between the basal cords do the striae appear closer.

Haplocochlias pauciliratus is a species which by its morphological characteristics (shape of the protoconch, shorter spire and shape of the umbilicus) is excluded from the preceding groups. It is close to the genus *Parviturbo* Pilsbry & McGinty, 1945. However, its general appearance, shape and regularity of the axial grooves, and the shape of the outer lip have convinced us to place it in *Haplocochlias*.

It can be distinguished from the fossil species *H. chipolanum* (Fig. 42G) because it has a higher number of spiral cords, the periumbilical cord is not so marked and the external lip has a simple margin, not scalloped, scarcely reflected outwards.

Haplocochlias bellus (Dall, 1889) (Figures 39-41)

Fossarus (Gottoina) bella Dall, 1889. *Bulletin of the Museum of Comparative Zoology*, 18: 272-273, pl. 28, fig. 10. [Type Locality: Sand Key, Florida, USA].

Type material: Holotype in MCZ (7461), examined.

Other material examined: USA, Florida: 3 s, station BIERFK-421, Carysfort Reef, Florida Keys, Monroe Co., 104 m (FMNH, 328628); 1 s, station BIERFK-447, Key Colony Beach, Florida Keys, Monroe Co., 77 m (FMNH, 333882).

Description: Original description in DALL (1889): "Shell small, white, solid, shaped much like *Littorina littorea*, having four and a half whorls and a minute glassy rounded nucleus. Radiating sculpture consisting of fine incremental striae and occasional irregularities of growth. Spiral sculpture of two sorts; 1st, fine spiral grooving covering the whole shell evenly and always present; 2d, strong spiral ridges, generally nine or ten on the last whorl, but sometimes smaller and more numerous, sometimes partly absent, sometimes so arranged as to tabulate the part of the whorl next the suture, and almost invariably smaller and weaker as they approach the base and the centre of the base. Suture distinct, not channelled; aperture simple, nearly circular, but the outer margin of its thickened edge angulated at the junction with the body; callus

continuous; columella arched, with a small chink, but no umbilicus behind it; this chink varies in size with different specimens. Aperture oblique, its upper margin a little depressed. Alt. 3.5 mm; max. diam. 3.5 mm".

Shell robust, as high as wide (HD: 1.00), spire formed by 4 ½ whorls of rapid growth. The protoconch has a little more than ¾ whorl, it is completely smooth and measures about 270 µm. The teleoconch has 3 ¾ whorl; it is ornamented with thick spiral, very prominent, cords that are duplicated and others, finer, located in the spaces between them; some marked growth lines, axial grooves in the interspaces of the first two whorls and micro tubercles all along the shell can also be observed. Taking the holotype in apertural view,

Figure 39A-C. *Haplocochlias bellus* (Dall, 1889). A-E: holotype, 3.5 mm, (MCZ); F: apex of the holotype.

Figura 39A-C. *Haplocochlias bellus* (Dall, 1889). A-E: holotipo, 3,5 mm, (MCZ); F: ápice del holotipo.

Figure 40. *Haplocochlias bellus* (Dall, 1889), sculpture and micro sculpture of the last whorl of the holotype.

Figura 40. *Haplocochlias bellus* (Dall, 1889), escultura y microescultura de la última vuelta del holotipo.

we can see 3 cords in the first whorl of the teleoconch, 4-5 in the second and 12 strong cords, some duplicated, on the last; in addition, numerous very fine spiral striae can be seen in the interspaces. The non adult specimen photographed (Fig. 41A), shows us a very

wide columella on its base, with a broad triangular depression in the area of intersection with the periumbilical cord; an external lip not widened and sharply scalloped at its margin. In the holotype, single adult specimen examined, the umbilicus is almost hidden by the reflec-

Figure 41. *Haplocochlias bellus* (Dall, 1889). A, B: juveniles, 2.3 and 1.47 mm, Station BIERFK-421, Carysfort Reef, Florida Keys, Monroe Co., Florida, USA (FMNH); C: protoconch, same shell as B; D: microsculpture of the last whorl, same shell as A.

Figura 41. Haplocochlias bellus (Dall, 1889). A, B: juveniles, 2,3 y 1,47 mm, estación BIERFK-421, Carysfort Reef, Florida Keys, Monroe Co., Florida, USA (FMNH); C: protoconcha, misma concha que B; D: microescultura de la última vuelta, misma concha que A.

tion of the columella and the outer lip is thickened slightly and is reflected outward.

Dimensions: Maximum reported size: 3.5 mm

Habitat: USA: Sand Key, 15 fms (27 m) (Dall, 1889); Carisfort Reef, Florida Keys, green mud, 104 m and Key Colony Beach, Florida Keys, muddy sand, 77 m in the present work.

Distribution: USA: North Carolina, East Florida, Florida Keys (Dall, 1889). Cuba: off Havana (Aguayo, 1935; see below). Range: 35°N to 23.15°N; 81.2°W to 76°W].

Remarks: This species has been placed in the genera *Fossarus* (*Gottoina*), *Fossarus* and *Parvoiturbo*. DALL (1889) comments: "This pretty little shell sometimes has the raised riblets reddish brown

against the waxen white of the rest. The nucleus is smaller and less elevated than in *Fossarus ambiguus*, from which, by the way, Gould's *F. pusillus* does not appear to differ specifically".

In relation to its systematic position DALL (1898) mentions: "I hesitated for some time as to whether this species should be described where I have placed it, or under *Cyclostrema*. In the absence of the operculum and of the soft parts, it is evident that the question as to its proper classification can only be decided provisionally, and with due reserve".

The record of AGUAYO (1935) for Cuba is considered dubious because it has never been confirmed later. Possibly the species could be confused with *H. ortizi*, which may have a similarity with *H. bellus*.

CONCLUSIONS AND COMMENTS

General information

In the present work, focused on the recent representatives of the genus *Haplocochlias* (family Skeneidae), we have studied 29 species. From these, 17 were previously known, 11 are described as new to science, and one more is presented as "sp." We have examined more than 600 specimens and shells from all the species from lots loaned by several museums (mainly MCZ, LACM and FMHN), as well as type photographs from other museums (ANSP, USNM) and private collections (see in abbreviations).

With such a numerous group of species and for simplicity of its study we have distributed them into smaller groups based on morphological similarity, assigning the name of each one to the oldest species present (except in one case): *cyclophoreus* group with 5 species; *swifti* group with 7; *ortizi* group with 2; *cubensis* group with 3; *moolenbeeki* group with 10 species, and two additional species which could not be fitted in the groups.

This genus is apparently only present in the Western Atlantic (Caribbean and neighbouring areas) and in the opposite West Central American Pacific coast. The number of species is

not equally distributed. Only 6 species were found in the Pacific while there were 23 in the Western Atlantic. As could be expected, the six Pacific species are grouped: three in the *cyclophoreus* group (*H. cyclophoreus*, *H. lucasensis* and *H. multiliratus*); and another three in the *moolenbeeki* group (*H. conceptionensis*, *H. erici* and *H. panamensis*).

This genus can be considered as only superficially studied due to the small size of its shells and the general lack of knowledge of its habitat, which could be interstitial or perhaps among rocks. For these reasons, the collection of living specimens of these species has been usually infrequent. Furthermore, their study requires SEM, not only because of their small size but also due to the necessity of revealing the microsculpture of the protoconch and teleoconch under higher magnification for species-level distinctions; all this makes the study and understanding of the group more challenging. In collections, shells from various localities are probably distinct species but were not distinguished due to lack of literature and diagnostic tools.

HICKMAN & MCLEAN (1990) consider that both *Haplocochlias* and *Parvi-*

turbo, "are genera from shallow-water with thickened lips". This statement is not entirely correct, because this study has demonstrated that *Haplocochlias* species are distributed from the sublittoral to the continental slope; their bathymetric range from 0 to 200 m.

There are at least 11 species which have been recorded living in bottoms deeper than 50 m (*H. compactus*, *H. swifti*, *H. williamsi*, *H. ortizi*, *H. arrondoi*, *H. nunezi*, *H. erici*, *H. francesae*, *H. panamensis*, *H. turbinus* and *H. bellus*); conversely only 3 species have been recorded at the intertidal level (*H. moolenbeeki*, *H. calidimaris* and *H. conceptionensis*). The species collected at greater depth (*H. compactus*, *H. bellus*, *H. panamensis* and *H. turbinus*) did not fit completely the generic profile of *Haplocochlias*. Nevertheless, some of their morphological characters are identified with those of this genus, and on this basis we have placed them in *Haplocochlias*.

The species that presents the widest geographical distribution is *H. nunezi*, found from Florida to Nicaragua, on both insular (Cuba, Bahamas and British Virgin Islands) and continental coasts (Florida, Mexico and Nicaragua). In the Bahamas this species occurs in high density as indicated by the large number of individuals collected in sediments. Another species with an apparently wide distribution is *H. swifti* which was found in most of the Caribbean coasts reaching Brazil, although some records may not be valid but a confusion with another species. A limited distribution is more common in most of the studied species: some of them can span two neighbouring countries: *H. pauciliratus* (Bermudas and Bahamas), *H. erici* (Panamá and Colombia), *H. compactus* (Florida, Louisiana, Cuba). But the most common is a smaller distribution which leads us to suppose that there is a high grade of speciation and so of endemism (*H. onaneyi*, Cuba; *H. garciai*, Honduras; *H. minusdentatus*, Bahamas; *H. loperi*, Turks and Caicos; *H. bieleri*, Florida; *H. ortizi*, Cuba; *H. arrondoi*, Cuba; etc).

In some areas (such as Florida and Cuba) we have found together several species: in Florida *H. compactus*, *H. swifti*,

H. bieleri, *H. calidimaris* and *H. francesae*; in Cuba *H. onaneyi*, *H. ortizi*, *H. cubensis*, *H. nunezi* and *H. pacorubioi*. This is not an unexpected pattern, considering that the evolutionary separation between them may be caused not by broad geographic isolation but by different habitat or different depths within the area where they are living. Also, both Florida and Cuba are among the most studied places in the Caribbean, so that most of the species existing there have been described. A similar situation may be still undetected in other areas which were not so well studied.

With respect to thickening of the outer lip, species here assigned to *Haplocochlias* do not present a common pattern unlike most of the *Parviturbo*, having species with a very thick lip, others with a thin lip, even expanded frontally, and a few with a simple and sometimes even slightly crenulated lip. We have been able to observe how in gerontic specimens, thus morphologically more complete, of species such as *H. nunezi*, *H. compactus* and *H. bellus*, some characters of the morphology of the shell may be variable. Particularly, the columella becomes thickened and reflected towards the umbilicus, closing it completely and making some of these shells look imperforate. Nevertheless, most of the adult individuals of the same species do not have such a developed columella and therefore, their umbilicus is not completely closed but reduced to a narrow fissure.

The protoconch of the studied shells is always short, with about $\frac{3}{4}$ of whorl after the nucleus (counted following the method of VERDUIN, 1976). Regarding sculpture, there are only two patterns across all the species: either smooth, or with 4-5 oblique cordlets (two only in one case). This character seems to be somewhat correlated with other morphological characters of the shell, as it appears very irregularly but with predominance of one of the states: in the *cyclophoreus* group there are 4 species with a smooth protoconch and one with cordlets; in the *swifti* group, all have cordlets, but in one species we did not have good material to

Table I. Compared characteristics of the *Haplocochlias* species. H= height; D= maximum diameter; H/D= ratio between height and diameter; SW= spire whorls; PSc= protoconch with sculpture; PS= protoconch smooth; PC= protoconch with cords; CW1= cords on the first whorl; CLW= cords on last whorl; VWL= very wide lip; WL= wide lip; DL= denticulate lip; EF= expanded frontally; CR= crenulated; SC= scalloped; S= simple lip.

Tabla I. Comparativa de características de las especies de *Haplocochlias*. H= altura; D= diámetro máximo; H/D= relación entre altura y diámetro; SW= vueltas de espira; PSc= protoconcha con escultura; PS= protoconcha lisa; PC= protoconcha con cordones; CW1= cordones en la primera vuelta; CLW= cordones en la última vuelta; VWL= labio muy ancho; WL= labio ancho; DL= labio denticulado; EF= expandido frontalmente; CR= crenulado; SC= festoneado; S= labio simple.

species	shell				protoconch		shell sculpture		lip
	H	D	H/D	SW	PSc	PC	CW1	CLW	
<i>H. cyclophoreus</i>	5.15	5.35	0.96	4 ¾	PS	220	4	42	VWL
<i>H. lucasensis</i>	1.7	1.6	1.06	3 ¾	PS	220	4	21	WL
<i>H. compactus</i>	1.63	1.7	0.96	3 ½	PS	220	3-4	22	WL
<i>H. risonaidenerya</i>	4.52	4.3	1.05	5 ¼	PS	200	3-4	24	VWL
<i>H. multiliratus</i>	1.69	1.94	0.82	4	PS	190	3-4	21	VWL
<i>H. swifti</i>	3,70	3,70	1,00	5	PC	220	2	24	DL
<i>H. onaneyi</i>	1,93	1,91	1,01	4	PC	240	2	18	DL
<i>H. garciae</i>	2,18	2,00	1,09	4 1/4	PC	210	2	17	DL
<i>H. williami</i>	1,80	?	?	2 3/4	?	?	2	20	DL
<i>H. minusdentatus</i>	1,25	1,05	1,19	3 1/4	PC	250	4	12	DL
<i>H. loperi</i>	1,29	1,26	1,02	3	PC	260	3	11	DL
<i>H. bieleri</i>	1,56	1,3	1,20	3 1/2	PC	230	2	25	DL
<i>H. ortizi</i>	2,70	3,00	0,90	4 1/2	PC	230	2	20	WL
<i>H. densistriatus</i>	2,15	2,37	0,91	4	PC	220	2	9	WL
<i>H. cubensis</i>	2,51	2,65	0,95	4 1/4	PC	240	3	75	EF
<i>H. arrondoi</i>	2,13	2,17	0,98	3 1/2	PC	240	3 - 4	32	EF
<i>H. harryleei</i>	3,03	3,11	0,97	4 3/4	PC	230	4	28	EF
<i>H. moolenbeeki</i>	4,4	4,7	1,03	5	PS	215	4	34	CR
<i>H. nunezi</i>	4,89	5,42	0,90	5	PC	290	4	53	CR
<i>H. calidimaris</i>	1,75	2	0,88	3 1/4	PC	260	3	10	SC
<i>H. pacorubioi</i>	2,81	2,50	1,12	4 1/2	PS	210	4	46	CR
<i>H. erici</i>	1,95	1,75	1,11	4	PS	170	4	16	CR
<i>H. conceptionensis</i>	5,6	5,60	1,00	5	PS	180	4	17	CR
<i>H. francesae</i>	3,15	3,40	0,96	4 1/2	PS	280	3 - 4	9	SC
<i>H. panamensis</i>	3,78	4,18	0,90	5	PS?	230	4 - 5	29	CR
<i>H. sp</i>	3,9	4,2	0,89	4 3/4	PC?	220	5	35	CR?
<i>H. turbinus</i>	2,75	3,25	0,85	4	PS?	240	3-4	24	CR?
<i>H. pauciliratus</i>	1,47	1,51	0,98	3	PS	250	3 or 4	12	S
<i>H. bellus</i>	3,5	3,5	1,00	4 1/2	PS	270	3 or 4	16-18	SC

examine this point. In *ortizi* and *cubensis* groups, all have cordlets; in the *moolenbeeki* group the predominance is for the smooth protoconchs (7 species); 2 have cordlets and in one this is dubious due to the poor condition of the protoconch; the two ungrouped species are smooth.

In Table I, a comparison of the characters of the different species is made. In order to facilitate the separation of the species in this group we present the following identification key for the genus pointing out the most important characters for each species.

Identification key

- 1 - Shell robust with a very thick aperture, not or weakly denticulate 2
 - Shell with outer lip very thick and internally denticulate 3
 - Shell with outer lip not very wide but frontally extended 4
 - Shell with a depressed area in the intersection of the outer lip, columella and peri-umbilical cord 5
 - Shell with the columella straight and widened at its base 6
 - Shell with simple lip, not thickened, denticulated or crenulated 7
- 2 - Shell without axial striae and size >5 mm *H. cyclophoreus*
 - Shell without axial striae, size <2 mm, smooth protoconch *H. compactus*
 - Shell without axial striae, size <2 mm, protoconch with spiral cordlets *H. lucasensis*
 - Shell with axial striae *H. risoneideneryae*
 - Shell with axial striae, size 2 mm and smooth protoconch *H. multiliratus*
- 3 - Outer lip with denticulation not very thick *H. swifti*
 - Outer lip strongly denticulate in its inner margin *H. garciai*
 - Outer lip with fine denticulation inside (in pairs) border of the lip prominent, umbilical fissure *H. onaneyi*
 - Outer lip with fine denticulation inside (in pairs) and closed umbilicus *H. bieleri*
 - Outer lip with fine denticulation and a very sharp angle at its periphery, like a shoulder *H. williami*
 - Outer lip with light denticulation and first whorl of teleoconch with 4 spiral cords *H. minusdentatus*
 - Outer lip with light denticulation and first whorl of teleoconch with 3 spiral cords *H. loperi*
- 4 - Shell with rounded periphery and 75 spiral cords in the last whorl *H. cubensis*
 - Shell with rounded periphery and 28 spiral cords in the last whorl *H. harryleei*
 - Teleoconch with 2 elevated spiral cords as small keels *H. arrondoii*
- 5 - Shell size > 5 mm and smooth protoconch *H. moolenbeeki*
 - Shell size > 5 mm, smooth protoconch and outer lip reflected *H. conceptionensis*
 - Shell size > 5 mm and protoconch with spiral cordlets *H. nunezi*
 - Shell size < 5 mm with outer lip crenulate scallop-shaped *H. calidimaris*
 - Shell size < 5 mm with spiral cords crossed by delicate axial threads *H. francesae*
 - Shell size < 5 mm and smooth protoconch *H. pacorubioi*
 - Shell size < 5 mm with columellar denticulation *H. panamensis*
 - Shell size < 5 mm with outer lip reflected *H. sp.*
 - Shell size < 5 mm with rounded periphery *H. turbinus*
 - Shell size < 5 mm with 3-4 thin spiral cordlets inside of the umbilicus *H. erici*
 - Shell size < 5 mm with spiral striae in the cord interspaces *H. bellus*
- 6 - Last whorl of teleoconch with 20 spiral cords *H. ortizi*
 - Last whorl of teleoconch with 9 spiral cords *H. densistriatus*
- 7 - Last whorl of teleoconch with 12 spiral cords *H. pauciliratus*

APPENDIX 1. Fossil species

There are hitherto only two species in the fossil record of the genus *Haplocochlias*: *Haplocochlias? dominicensis* Aguayo, 1949 from the Middle

Miocene of the Dominican Republic, and *Fossarus (Gottoina) mundulus* Guppy, 1896 from the Oligocene of Jamaica.

Other species from the Eocene of Alabama, Oligocene of Florida, Miocene of North Carolina and Miocene and Pliocene of Florida, were described by DALL (1892): *Gibbula americana*, *Collonia claibornensis*, *Collonia chipolana*, *Collonia elegantula* and *Cyclostrema chipolanum*, additional species that could be considered, in our opinion, as belonging to the genus *Haplocochlias* by their general appearance. Two of them, *Collonia chipolana* and *Collonia elegantula* were later transferred by GARDNER (1947) to the genus *Gelasinostoma*, family Turbinidae. This action already was

commented on by HICKMAN & MCLEAN (1990: 143) who indicated: "*In the New World, Gelasinostoma Gardner, 1947, from the Plio-Pleistocene of the western Atlantic seems to be close to Haplocochlias*".

Below we associate each of the mentioned fossil species, providing the data that we consider of greater interest and their original illustration. As the present work focuses on the Recent species of the genus *Haplocochlias*, we have not revised the type material and therefore we will not make a final assessment with regard to their generic placement.

Haplocochlias? dominicensis Aguayo, 1949

Haplocochlias? dominicensis Aguayo, 1949. *Revista de la Sociedad Malacológica "Carlos de la Torre"*, 6 (3): 92, pl. 4, fig. 8. [Type locality: Gurabo Formation, Middle Miocene, Dominican Republic].

Type material: Holotype in Museo Poesy, Universidad de La Habana (n° 11819). Not examined.

Description: Original description in AGUAYO (1949).

Dimensions of the holotype: Height 2.6 mm. Diameter 2.8 mm.

The species is characterized by two prominent spiral cords which are limit and angulate the last whorl of the teleoconch whose profile is practically straight.

Remarks: This is a fossil species from the Middle Miocene Gurabo formation, of the Dominican Republic. After the original description of the species, AGUAYO (1949) wrote: "*La posición genérica es dudosa, pues el único examinado posee las vueltas apicales desgastadas. Por*

otra parte, la fuerte escultura espiral y la presencia del ombligo, separa esta especie de Haplocochlias cyclophoreus Cpr., de las costas de California, a la cual se parece sin embargo, por la forma general y la naturaleza de la abertura. Es también similar a Haplocochlias swifti Vanatta, 1913 de Sto. Thomas, Antillas Menores, pero la escultura es muy diferente, así como la naturaleza de la abertura".

The only species with which it bears a resemblance is *H. pacorubioi*. It differs by having the periphery of the last whorl limited by two cords which form an angle, producing an almost straight profile in apertural view.

Fossarus (Gottoina) mundulus Guppy in Guppy & Dall, 1896 (Figure 42A)

Fossarus (Gottoina) mundulus Guppy, 1896. *Proceedings of the United States National Museum*, 19 (1110): 320, pl. 27 fig. 16. [Oligocene of Jamaica, Vendryes].

Type material: Deposited in USNM (n° 107093 and 107094) (ex Coll. Guppy n° 2291). Not examined.

Description: See GUPPY & DALL (1896). Holotype size: Height. 3 mm, diameter 2.75 mm.

Remarks: The great coincidence between the figure of *Fossarus (Gottoina)*

mundulus Guppy, 1896 (pl. 27 fig. 16) and that of *Fossarus (Gottoina) bella* Dall, 1889 (*Bulletin of the Museum of Comparative Zoology*, 18, pl. 28 fig. 10) is quite curious, and we might even conclude

Figure 42. Some fossil species discussed in the text. A: *Fossarus (Gottoina) mundulus* Guppy, 1896 in Guppy & Dall, 1896 (original figure pl. 27 fig. 16); B: *Gibbula americana* Dall, 1892 (original figure pl. 22 fig. 32); C: *Collonia claibornensis* Dall, 1892 (original figure pl. 22 fig. 26); D: *Collonia chipolana* Dall, 1892 (reproduced from Gardner, 1947, pl. 62 fig. 12); E: *Gelasinostoma elegantula*, shell in NMR (62252); F-G: *Collonia elegantula* Dall, 1892 (original figure pl. 19 fig. 3-4); H: *Cyclostrema chipolanum* Dall, 1892 (original figure pl. 22 fig. 35).

Figura 42. Algunas especies fósiles discutidas en el texto. A: *Fossarus (Gottoina) mundulus* Guppy, 1896 in Guppy & Dall, 1896 (figura original lám. 27 fig. 16); B: *Gibbula americana* Dall, 1892 (figura original lám. 22 fig. 32); C: *Collonia claibornensis* Dall, 1892 (figura original lám. 22 fig. 26); D: *Collonia chipolana* Dall, 1892 (reproducido de Gardner, 1947, lám. 62 fig. 12); E: *Gelasinostoma elegantula*, concha en NMR (62252); F-G: *Collonia elegantula* Dall, 1892 (figura original lám. 19 fig. 3-4); H: *Cyclostrema chipolanum* Dall, 1892 (figura original lám. 22 fig. 35).

that it is the same species. Also it is curious that GUPPY & DALL (1896), when they described F. (G) *mundulus*, did not comment on a very similar species described by Dall just a few years earlier. They nevertheless made the fol-

lowing comment: "This species is not unlike some larger Recent forms found in deep water off the southeastern coast of the United States", which we think may allude to *Fossarus (Gottoina) bella*, but without an explicit mention.

Gibbula americana Dall, 1892 (Figure 42B)

Gibbula americana Dall, 1892. *Transactions of the Wagner Free Institute of Science of Philadelphia*, 3 (2): 389, pl. 22, fig. 32 [Miocene, Duplin County, North Carolina].

Type material: Holotype (USNM 113010) from near Natural Well, Duplin County, North Carolina (listed in SCHUCHERT *ET AL.*, 1905: 287).

Remarks: In addition to its general shape, the aperture presents many similarities with some Recent *Haplocochlias* species (outer lip expanded outward and

columella widened at its base and reflected towards the umbilicus, but without reaching occluding it) as *Haplocochlias ortizi* and *Haplocochlias densicostatus*.

Collonia claibornensis Dall, 1892 (Figure 42C)

Collonia claibornensis Dall, 1892. *Transactions of the Wagner Free Institute of Science of Philadelphia* 3, pt. 2, p. 388, pl. 22, fig. 26 (Eocene, Claiborne, Alabama).

Type material: Holotype (USNM 113002), listed in SCHUCHERT *ET AL.*, 1905: 155.

Remarks: DALL (1892: 386) in relation with the species of the genus *Collonia* Gray, 1850 says: "The general form of the shells of this genus is more like an elevated *Cyclostrema* than a heavy turbinate *Omphalius*, and the outer lip is expanded and slightly thickened. The sulcus in the lip and the peculiar umbilical forbid its association with *Cyclostrema*, and the thickened

and reflected lip distinguishes it from *Solariella*; and from *Haplocochlias*, otherwise very similar, by its umbilical characters".

In the original figuration we can observe that the outer lip is expanded, and at the base of the columella there is a depressed area, typical of some species of *Haplocochlias*.

Gelasinostoma chipolanum (Dall, 1892) (Figure 42D)

Collonia chipolana Dall, 1892. *Transactions of the Wagner Free Institute of Science*, 3 (2): 387 (Oligocene, Calhoun County, Florida).

Gelasinostoma chipolanum (Dall, 1892): Gardner, 1947. *United States Geological Survey Professional Paper*, 142-H, p. 612, pl. LXII, fig. 12.

Type material: Holotype (USNM 113001).

Remarks: GARDNER (1947) comments: "The shell though immature, is an unmistakable *Collonia*, and I have described it, lest it should be lost sight of, being the only repre-

sentative of the group in the Chipola Miocene" and "No other representative of the species or of the genus has been found at any horizon in the Alum Bluff group".

Gelasinostoma elegantulum (Dall, 1892) (Figure 42E-G)

Collonia elegantula Dall, 1892. *Transactions of the Wagner Free Institute of Science*, 3 (2): 386, pl. 19, figs. 3, 4 (Pliocene, Caloosahatchie River, near Fort Thompson, Florida).

Gelasinostoma elegantulum (Dall, 1892): Gardner, 1947. *United States Geological Survey Professional Paper*, 142-H: 611 (type species of *Gelasinostoma* by original designation).

Type material: "Cotypes" (syntypes) USNM 112996 from Caloosahatchie River, near Fort Thompson, Florida (listed in SCHUCHERT *ET AL.*, 1905: 155).

Material examined: *Gelasinostoma elegantula* (Dall, 1892): Natural History Museum Rotterdam (NMR 66252), Pliocene, Tamiami Formation, Florida.

Remarks: The figured holotype as well as the specimen deposited in the NMR (66252) are very similar *H. onaneyi*, but the latter lacks the depression in the peristome and the strong periumbilical cord

present in *G. elegantulum*. GARDNER (1947) considers the depression of the peristome at the extremity of the umbilical keel as a distinctive character not shared by any other group.

Cyclostrema chipolanum Dall, 1892 (Figure 42H)

Cyclostrema chipolanum Dall, 1892. *Transactions of the Wagner Free Institute of Science of Philadelphia*, 3 (2): 420, pl. 22, fig. 35 (Miocene, Bailey's Ferry, Chipola River, Calhoun County, Florida).

Type material: Holotype (USNM 112660), listed in SCHUCHERT *ET AL.*, 1905: 194.

Remarks: The original figuration of this species resembles closely in outline, form and number of spiral cords and shape of the opening and external lip the new species described as *H. pauciliratus*

from Bahamas and Bermuda Islands. It differs because this species has a lesser number of spiral cords, a wider periumbilical cord and the external lip reflected outwards apparently scalloped.

APPENDIX 2. Genera not related to *Haplocochlias*

Hereunder we present some comparative information on the genera *Got-*

toina and *Lophocochlias* in some occasion considered related.

Genus *Gottoina* A. Adams, 1863

Gottoina A. Adams, 1863. *Proceedings of the Zoological Society of London*, 1863: 110-113. [Type species by subsequent designation (HIGO, CALLOMON & GOTO, 1999): *Conradia* (*Gottoina*) *sulcifera* A. Adams, 1863. Gotto, Japan.

Original description: "Testa turbinoidea seu trochiformis, imperforata; anfractibus transversim liratis. Apertura ovata; labio simplici, arcuato".

Distribution: Japan and Philippines.

Remarks: *Gottoina* A. Adams, 1863 was described as a subgenus of

Conradia, family Fossaridae. Until recently both genera were placed in Skeneinae, but HICKMAN (2013) accommodated *Conradia* in a new family Crosseolidae Hickman, 2013 (still in Vetigastropoda).

Gottoina sulcifera A. Adams, 1863 (Figure 43)

Conradia (*Gottoina*) *sulcifera* A. Adams, 1863. *Proceedings of Zoological Society of London*, 1863: 110-113. [Type locality: Gotto, Japan].

Type species: One syntype deposited at Museum Victoria, Australia (n° 31453). Not examined.

Other material examined: 1 s, Olango Island, Baring, Philippines, dredged at 180 m (CFR); 2 s, Mactan Island, Punta Engano, Philippines 180-250 m (CFR).

Description: Original description in ADAMS (1863: 113): “*testa depresso-turbinata, albida, solida, rimata, spira obtusa; anfractibus 3 1/2, convexis, liris transversis validis cequalibus, interstitiis longitudinaliter concinne striatis, ornatis; apertura ovata; labio subincrassato, arcuato; labro margine crenulato. Gotto, 48 fathoms.*”

The shell is of small size, robust, turbiniform, higher than wide (H/D: 1.25), of dirty whitish/yellowish colour; its spire is composed of 4 ¼ rapidly-expanding whorls. The protoconch is totally smooth, little more than ¾ whorl and measures about 240 µm in diameter. The teleoconch has 3 ½ whorls and is ornamented by strong cords and narrow, deep spiral sulci, with microtubercles and axial striae. Three spiral cords can be seen on the first and second whorls, and 12 on the last; the axial striae cross the spiral cords, more

visible on the basal cords; the number of the axial striae increase in number as they approach the last whorl. The shell is imperforate, without even a chink exposed. Aperture rounded, columella arched; no callous coat can be seen in the parietal area. Outer lip sharp, a little modified by the presence of the spiral sulci in the area close to the columella where it is undulant due the width and depth of the sulci.

Dimensions: 3.30 mm in height and 2.62 mm in diameter.

Habitat: Shell dredged at 170 m depth in the Olango Islands, Philippines.

Distribution: Gotto, Japan (A. ADAMS, 1863); Olango and Mactan Islands, Philippines (our material).

Remarks: The shell is imperforate. The modification of the outer lip by the spiral sulci distinguishes this genus from others with imperforate shells.

Genus *Lophocochlias* Pilsbry, 1921

Lophocochlias Pilsbry, 1921. *Proceedings of the Academy of Natural Sciences, Philadelphia*, 72: 377.

[Type species by monotypy: *Haplocochlias* (*Lophocochlias*) *minutissimus* Pilsbry, 1921, Mokapu Point, Oahu, Hawaii. Recent species].

Distribution: Tropical Indo-West Pacific. Western Pacific, Polynesia.

Remarks: Described originally as a subgenus of *Haplocochlias*. PILSBRY (1921) says: “By the well-developed varix this shell resembles *Haplocochlias* or *Liotia*. I have placed it in the former genus with doubt. It differs by the very strong sculpture and the open though not wide umbilicus, which may characterize a separate section *Lophocochlias*”.

KAY (1979) used *Lophocochlias* as a valid genus and retained it tentatively in Skeneidae.

Nevertheless HICKMAN & MCLEAN (1990) do not include *Lophocochlias* in the living genera of Skeneidae.

The systematic position of *Lophocochlias* in Skeneidae is the direct consequence of being initially described as a subgenus of *Haplocochlias* and later considered a valid genus. Yet this does not

seem to be the case. In our opinion, the striking morphology of its protoconch does not relate to any known skeneid. Its correct placement will depend on anatomical, radular, and opercular information which is not available now.

Some portals such as GBIF (Global Biodiversity Information Facility) place *Lophocochlias* in Tornidae, but we were not able to find a reason for this systematic placement. Others, such as OBIS Indo-Pacific Mollusca Database, give as the current name *Haplocochlias minutissimus* instead of *Lophocochlias minutissimus*.

Only two species appear related to this genus: *Lophocochlias minutissimus* (Pilsbry, 1921), a Recent species from Oahu, Hawaii and *Lophocochlias paucicarinatus* Ladd 1966, a Cenozoic fossil, from the Miocene of the Marshall Islands.

Figure 43. *Gottoina sulcifera* A. Adams, 1863. A: shell, diameter 2.25 mm, Baring, Olango Island, Philippines, dredged at 180 m; B: shell, 2.7 mm, Punta Engaño, Mactan Island, Philippines, 180-250 m. C: protoconch, same shell as B; D: detail of sculpture.

Figura 43. Gottoina sulcifera A. Adams, 1863. A: concha, diámetro 2,25 mm, Baring, Isla de Olango, Filipinas, dragado en 180 m; B: concha, 2,7 mm, Punta Engaño, Isla de Mactan, Filipinas, 180-250 m. C: protoconcha, misma concha que B; D: detalle de la escultura.

Lophocochlias minutissimus (Pilsbry, 1921) (Figure 44)

Haplocochlias (*Lophocochlias*) *minutissimus* Pilsbry, 1921. *Proceedings of the Academy of Natural Sciences, Philadelphia*, 72: 377. [Type locality: Mokapu Point, Oahu, Hawaii].

Type material: 4 specimens deposited in ANSP (107930). Not examined.

Other material examined: Jordan: 13 s, Aqaba, 10-20 m (MHNS).

Description: Original description in PILSBRY (1921: 377): “The very small shell is umbilicate, turbinate, not nacreous, white with a conic brownish spire. The first whorl appears to be smooth; on the second fine radial folds or puckering appears below the suture, becoming coarser on the following whorl. The last whorl has six strong, smooth spiral keels, narrower than the intervals, which are flat, and crossed by numerous retractively axial threads, which are much narrower than their intervals. Within the umbilicus two rather small spiral cords are seen. The aperture is quite oblique, subcircular. The outer lip is strengthened by a rounded external rib or varix a short distance behind the edge”.

Length 1 mm, diameter 0.9 mm; 4 1/3 whorls.

KAY (1979) extended the original description: “Shell turbiniform; spirally keeled and with fine axial threads; white. Protoconch of two and one-half acute, brown whorls, the apical smooth, the others with oblique axial ribs; teleoconch of three convex whorls, the last the largest. Sculpture: apical whorl with granular axial ribs and spiral threads, the next with two and the last with six spiral keels; interspaces between the spiral keels of greater diameter than the keels, shallow, crossed by numerous axial threads. Aperture: subcircular, oblique; outer lip with an external varix; umbilicus wide and deep; operculum circular, multi-spiral, horny. Color: white”.

Habitat: Subtidal, common in sediments to depths of 30 m and also in tide pools around bases of seaweeds and on solution benches (KAY, 1979). It is an epifaunal species which feeds on detritus.

Distribution: Tropical Indo-West Pacific: Oceania: Polynesia: Hawaiian Islands; French Polynesia: Tuamotu Archipelago; Western Pacific: Marshall Islands (OBIS – Indo Pacific Mollusca Database). From Red Sea in present work.

Remarks: Miocene fossils are reported from the Marshall Islands and Fiji, and a Pleistocene fossil from Tonga (LADD, 1966). PILSBRY (1921), in an attempt to place this species in a correct genus, created the subgenus *Lophocochlias*, which was considered different from the nominal subgenus *Haplocochlias* due to its stronger sculpture and an open umbilicus. Actually, these morphological characters (lip thickening, wide umbilicus) are present in many turbinoid species; in spite of this, the protoconch appears to be an exclusive character which distinguishes it from Liotiidae and Skeneidae; it is a spectacular protoconch by its development and complex ornamentation. KAY (1979: 56) comments: “The veliger larvae exhibit both rissoacean and cerithiacean features, resembling rissoids with respect to the inflated shell and cerithids with respect to sculpture and rounded aperture”.

LADD (1966) and SEPKOSKI (2002) list *Lophocochlias* in the family Skeneidae, but these are essentially palaeontological compilations and we think that without anatomical, radular, and opercular study it is impossible to place *Lophocochlias* in the proper position with any confidence.

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Figure 44. *Lophocochlias minutissima* (Pilsbry, 1921). A-C: shells, 0.91, 0.85, 0.7 mm, Aqaba, Jordan, 25 m (MHNS); D: protoconch; E: sculpture.

Figura 44. *Lophocochlias minutissima* (Pilsbry, 1921). A-C: conchas, 0,91, 0,85, 0,7 mm, Aqaba, Jordania, 25 m (MHNS); D: protoconcha; E: escultura.

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